

SCIANCE

D8.1

**Communication,
Dissemination and
Exploitation Strategy**

Status: SUBMITTED

Dissemination Level: Public

Abstract	
Key words	Please provide between 1 and 6 keywords
<p>The SCIANCE Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement framework defines an integrated approach to building visibility, fostering stakeholder engagement, and ensuring the uptake, exploitation, and long-term impact of project results within the emerging European AI in Science ecosystem. It combines coordinated communication, structured dissemination, and continuous engagement to support the co-creation, validation, and exploitation of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).</p> <p>The communication strategy establishes a coherent project identity and consistent messaging across channels, structured on a common branding framework, aligned with European Commission requirements, and the broader RAISE ecosystem. A central component is the RAISE Digital Hub, which integrates curated content and interactive engagement through a two-layer architecture, comprising a content platform and a community forum. This enables both structured publication of project outputs and continuous stakeholder interaction via Working Groups, consultations, and co-creation processes.</p> <p>The dissemination and exploitation strategy is structured around community building and co-creation, visibility and awareness, and dissemination and uptake. These are implemented through an events programme including the AIS Summits, thematic workshops, consultation activities, and a final dissemination event, complemented by active participation in key European and international policy and research forums. External participation ensures alignment with EU initiatives and research infrastructures such as EOSC, EuroHPC JU, and ESFRI, while strengthening pathways for uptake and exploitation of SCIANCE outputs.</p> <p>Overall, the framework provides a structured, adaptive, and evidence-based approach to communication, dissemination, exploitation, and engagement, ensuring that SCIANCE results are co-developed with stakeholders, widely adopted, and embedded within the wider European AI Science ecosystem.</p>	

Revision History			
Version	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
V 0.1	07/05/2026	First draft	Magdalena Brus (EGI Foundation, EGI.eu) Gwen Franck (EGI Foundation, EGI.eu) Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE, OA) Jonas L'Haridon (European Science Foundation, ESF)
V 0.1	18/05/2026	First draft review	Eszter Fay (DG RTD, European Commission) Laura Roman (DG RTD, European Commission) Daniel Djamo (Big Data Value Association, BDVA)
V 0.2	21/05/2026	Second draft	Magdalena Brus (EGI Foundation, EGI.eu) Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE, OA)
V1	29/05/2026	Submitted Version	Magdalena Brus (EGI Foundation, EGI.eu)

Document Description	
Work Package 8	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy
Document Type	Deliverable
Document Status	FINAL/Living Document Version 1.0
Dissemination Level	Public
Copyright Status	This material by Parties of the SCIANCE Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.
Lead partner	EGI.eu
Document Link	10.5281/zenodo.20446206
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.20446206
Author(s)	Magdalena Brus (EGI Foundation, EGI) Gwen Franck (EGI Foundation, EGI) Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE, OA) Jonas L'Haridon (European Science Foundation, ESF)
Reviewer(s)	Eszter Fay (DG RTD, European Commission) Laura Roman (DG RTD, European Commission) Daniel Djamo (Big Data Value Association, BDVA)
Approved by	SCIANCE Management Committee

Table of Contents

1 Executive Strategy	4
1.1 Purpose of the CDE Strategy	4
1.2 Scope and Structure of the Document	4
1.3 Link to SCIANCE Objectives and Expected Impact	4
1.4 Relation to SRIA Development and RAISE	4
2 Objectives of the CDE Strategy	5
2.1 Communication objectives	5
2.2 Engagement & dissemination objectives	6
2.3 Exploitation objectives	7
3 Stakeholder Mapping & Engagement	8
3.1 Key Strategic Parties	12
3.2 Stakeholder Engagement Lifecycle (M1–M30)	27
4 Communication Strategy	29
4.1 Communication Approach	29
4.2 Branding and Visual Identity for SCIANCE and RAISE	29
4.3 Communication & dissemination toolkit	29
4.4 Communication Channels and Tools	30
4.5 RAISE Digital Hub	31
4.6 Targeted Communication Campaigns	33
5 Dissemination Strategy	34
5.1 Dissemination Approach	34
5.2 Events programme	34
5.3 Training and capacity building (RAISE Academy)	36
5.4 Domains	36
5.4 Summary of Key Dissemination Activities	37
6 Work Plan	38
6.1 Key deliverables and milestones	38
6.2 Partner responsibilities	38
7 Monitoring, Evaluation, and KPIs	39
7.1 Key Performance Indicators by Activity	39
7.2 Data Collection and Analytics	40
7.3 Adaptive Strategy and Continuous Improvement	41
8 Vocabulary	42

1 Executive Strategy

1.1 Purpose of the CDE Strategy

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy of SCIANCE defines a coordinated framework to maximise the visibility, engagement, participation, and long-term impact of the project activities and its outputs, including the Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SRIA), the infrastructure roadmap, and the RAISE supporting pilot functions.

SCIANCE operates as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that aims to structure AI-enabled scientific research in Europe through a bottom-up, community-driven approach. Within this context, the CDE strategy ensures that scientific communities, research infrastructures, policymakers, industry, civil society and other stakeholders are effectively engaged in co-creating and adopting the project outcomes.

The strategy is designed to be a stand-alone operational framework guiding communication, dissemination, engagement and exploitation activities throughout the project lifecycle, while remaining fully aligned with European Commission priorities on AI in Science and the emerging RAISE ecosystem.

1.2 Scope and Structure of the Document

This CDE strategy is structured around four interlinked pillars:

- 1 **Communication Strategy:** ensuring awareness, positioning, and trust across stakeholder groups, including coordination of messaging across SCIANCE and RAISE-related activities.
- 2 **Dissemination Strategy:** supporting uptake of project's outputs, including the SRIA, infrastructure roadmap, AI in Science evidence base and more.
- 3 **Engagement Strategy:** ensuring structured, inclusive, and iterative interaction with stakeholders across Research Communities, AI Experts & AI Researchers, Research Infrastructures, E-Infrastructures & Scientific Facilities, Policy Makers & Funding Organisations, Civil Society, Industry & Innovation Actors, AISWGs as a key expert co-creation interface and the SCIANCE Strategic Advisory Board as a strategic advisory interface. This pillar enables co-creation, validation, and continuous refinement of SCIANCE outputs through mechanisms such as workshops, AIS Summits, consultations, working groups, and the RAISE Digital Hub.
- 4 **Exploitation Strategy:** ensuring continuity, long-term usability and integration of project results within European research ecosystems.

1.3 Link to SCIANCE Objectives and Expected Impact

The CDE strategy directly supports the achievement of SCIANCE's core objectives by enabling visibility, uptake, and sustained use of project outputs across all stakeholder groups.

In particular, it contributes to:

- 01 Mapping the European AI in Science landscape, by ensuring broad dissemination and validation of the evidence base through stakeholder engagement and digital channels.
- 02 Co-defining strategic research and innovation priorities, by enabling structured consultation processes that feed directly into the SRIA development.
- 03 Assessing infrastructure requirements, by facilitating dialogue between research communities, infrastructures, and policymakers on gap analysis and upgrade scenarios.
- 04 Enabling community building and sustainability, by establishing long-term engagement mechanisms through the RAISE Digital Hub, organisation of events and AIS Summits, and the RAISE Secretariat pilot.

The expected impact of the CDE strategy is to ensure that SCIANCE outputs are not only disseminated but actively adopted, validated, and embedded into European research and innovation ecosystems.

1.4 Relation to SRIA Development and RAISE

The CDE strategy is intrinsically linked to both the development of the SRIA and the emergence of the Resource for AI Science in Europe (RAISE). RAISE is a European Commission initiative under the European Strategy for AI in Science and the Apply AI Strategy designed to establish a coordinated European framework for AI-enabled scientific research. It aims to bring together scientific communities, research infrastructures, AI expertise, and policy actors through shared resources, coordination mechanisms, and long-term support structures.

In this context, communication, dissemination, and engagement are not downstream activities, but core enabling mechanisms that support co-creation, validation, and long-term adoption of SCIANCE outputs.

1.4.1 SRIA Development

The SRIA is a central output of SCIANCE and is co-developed through structured and iterative engagement with scientific communities, AI experts, research infrastructures, policymakers, industry, and other relevant stakeholders. The CDE strategy underpins this process by ensuring that:

- SRIA priorities are co-created through iterative consultation cycles across domains and stakeholder groups
- Feedback from workshops, AIS Summits, and digital engagement tools facilitated by the RAISE Digital Hub engagement layer, is systematically collected and integrated
- Domain-specific and cross-domain AI for Science priorities are validated through inclusive and multi-level participation
- The SRIA reflects both scientific excellence and alignment with European policy and strategic priorities

Through this approach, the CDE strategy ensures that the SRIA is community-driven, evidence-based, and broadly endorsed, supporting its uptake and long-term relevance.

1.4.2 Relation to RAISE

SCIANCE contributes directly to the development of RAISE by acting as a pilot coordination structure for its early implementation. As a distributed initiative implemented through multiple projects and coordination activities, RAISE relies on coherent communication, stakeholder alignment, and shared engagement mechanisms.

Within this context, the CDE strategy supports the operationalisation and coherence of the RAISE ecosystem by:

- Enabling early deployment and use of key RAISE components including Digital Hub, AIS Summits, and the RAISE Academy
- Ensuring coherent and aligned communication across distributed initiatives contributing to RAISE
- Applying European Commission communication and branding rules, recognising that RAISE does not constitute an independent brand but must be communicated within EC and SCIANCE visual identity frameworks applying the RAISE Branding and Co-branding Guidelines
- Supporting transitional governance and coordination mechanisms that facilitate ecosystem alignment until the establishment of a dedicated RAISE Secretariat

Through these functions, SCIANCE acts as an interim coordination and alignment layer, ensuring that communication, dissemination, and engagement activities across the AI in Science ecosystem are consistent, interoperable, and strategically aligned, while laying the foundations for the long-term sustainability of RAISE.

2 Objectives of the CDE Strategy

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy is designed to ensure that SCIANCE outputs are visible, understood, actively used, and sustainably integrated within the European AI in Science ecosystem. It supports both the immediate project objectives and the longer-term ambition of establishing a coordinated European framework for AI-enabled scientific research.

2.1 Communication objectives

The communication objectives focus on establishing SCIANCE as a trusted and authoritative reference point for AI in Science in Europe. In particular, the strategy aims to:

- 01** Increase awareness of SCIANCE and RAISE objectives, activities, and outputs among scientific communities, AI researchers, infrastructures, policymakers, industry, civil society and other stakeholders
- 02** Position SCIANCE as a key coordination and support initiative within the emerging European AI in Science ecosystem and its link to RAISE
- 03** Supporting the deployment and growth of RAISE by creating synergies and stimulating a cross-disciplinary dynamic among excellent researchers and labs working with AI,
- 04** Ensure consistent and coherent messaging across all project outputs, reinforcing scientific credibility and policy relevance

- 05 Build trust through transparent communication, high-quality dissemination materials, and alignment with European Commission priorities
- 06 Strengthen visibility of SCIANCE and AI in Science ecosystem through coordinated branding, digital channels, and participation in key European events and networks.

2.2 Engagement & dissemination objectives

The engagement and dissemination objectives ensure that SCIANCE is not only communicated but actively co-created with stakeholders and embedded in existing research and policy ecosystems. The strategy aims to:

- 01 Enable structured co-creation of the SRIA through iterative stakeholder consultation processes
- 02 Facilitate continuous engagement with scientific communities, AI experts, infrastructures, and policy actors via workshops, AIS Summits, numerous other audiences in the context of highly relevant events for the AI in Science community and the RAISE Digital Hub
- 03 Ensure broad and inclusive participation across disciplines, sectors, and geographical regions, including underrepresented communities
- 04 Support knowledge transfer across domains by identifying cross-disciplinary AI for Science opportunities and sharing good practices
- 05 Promote uptake and reuse of project outputs, including the SRIA, infrastructure roadmap, and AI in Science evidence base, across European research and innovation ecosystems
- 06 Strengthen long-term community building through sustained interaction mechanisms such as the Digital Hub, working groups, and capacity-building activities (e.g. RAISE Academy).

The engagement and dissemination objectives ensure that SCIANCE is not only communicated to stakeholders, but actively developed with them through structured co-creation, consultation, validation and strategic alignment. The strategy supports the development of the AI in Science Evidence Base, the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), the AI in Science Roadmap, the Good-practice registry and the future RAISE ecosystem by connecting WP1 evidence generation, WP2/WP3 co-creation, WP4 feasibility and roadmap development, and WP5 SRIA integration. The RAISE Digital Hub acts as the central engagement and access layer, supporting surveys, feedback tools, thematic forums, Living SRIA consultation threads, public online consultation, targeted consultation and transparent summaries showing how stakeholder input is considered.

Enable evidence-informed co-creation of the SRIA and AI in Science Roadmap

To support structured co-creation of scientific priorities, AI for Science research and innovation priorities, infrastructure gaps, upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms, using WP1 state-of-the-art reviews, landscape analysis and the Good-practice registry as the common Evidence Base.

Mobilise the AI in Science stakeholder ecosystem through clear engagement pathways

To engage research communities across scientific disciplines, AI researchers and technology experts, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and scientific facilities, policy makers and funding organisations, civil society, and industry and innovation actors through the appropriate mix of co-creation, consultation, review, validation and strategic alignment.

To engage domain scientists across the five scientific pilot areas and wider scientific disciplines, together with research communities, scientific networks and societies, AI researchers and technology experts, research infrastructures, e-infrastructures and scientific facilities, policy makers and funding organisations, civil society, and industry and innovation actors. Engagement will be organised through the appropriate mix of co-creation, consultation, review, validation and strategic alignment, ensuring that scientific priorities, AI for Science opportunities, infrastructure needs, cooperation mechanisms and SRIA recommendations are shaped by the relevant communities and stakeholder groups.

Strengthen the role of AISWGs as the expert co-creation and review layer

To use the domain and cross-cutting AI in Science Working Groups (AISWGs) to provide structured expert input before, during and after WP2/WP3 workshops, including review of draft priorities, infrastructure dependencies, consultation summaries, consensus points, dissenting views and cross-AISWG dependencies.

Support consultation and traceability through the RAISE Digital Hub

To use the RAISE Digital Hub as an engagement layer, not only as a content repository, to host consultation materials, surveys, feedback forms, thematic discussions, Good-practice submissions, Living SRIA threads, consultation summaries and transparent records of how stakeholder input feeds into the SRIA and Roadmap.

Use AIS Summits as high-level visibility, consultation and validation moments

To connect SCIANCE engagement activities with AIS Summits where feasible, using them as moments for visibility, matchmaking, community feedback, public or targeted consultation, validation of emerging outputs, and alignment with the wider European AI in Science ecosystem.

Ensure inclusive, multi-level and cross-sectoral participation

To promote balanced participation across scientific domains, AI communities, infrastructures, industry, policy, civil society, countries, career stages and underrepresented groups, while using clear engagement levels such as co-create, consult, review/validate and advise.

Facilitate cross-domain knowledge transfer and good-practice exchange

Promote reuse of the AI in Science Evidence Base, Good-practice registry, AI for Science use cases, interdisciplinary cooperation models, infrastructure requirements and lessons learned across the five scientific pilot areas and cross-cutting AI-related topics.

Align SCIANCE outputs with European initiatives, infrastructures and policy frameworks

Use targeted consultation and SAB input to support strategic alignment with European and national priorities, including relevant AI, Open Science, EOSC, ESFRI, EuroHPC, AI Factories, European AI research and innovation ecosystem actors, and policy and regulatory frameworks.

Promote uptake and reuse of SCIANCE outputs

Disseminate the SRIA, AI in Science Roadmap, Evidence Base, Good-practice registry, consultation summaries and capacity-building materials through trusted research, infrastructure, policy, industry, civil society and communication multiplier channels, supporting adoption beyond the project lifetime.

Support continuity towards RAISE and long-term community building

Use the RAISE Secretariat, RAISE Digital Hub, AISWGs, AIS Summits and RAISE Academy to maintain stakeholder relationships, support capacity building for decision-makers, preserve project knowledge and prepare the transition towards a long-term RAISE coordination structure.

2.3 Exploitation objectives

The SCIANCE project will ensure that key project outputs are taken up, reused, and sustained beyond the project lifetime as part of the emerging European AI in Science ecosystem. As a Coordination and Support Action, SCIANCE will focus its exploitation efforts on strategic adoption, policy uptake, community ownership, and the institutionalisation of coordination mechanisms for AI-enabled science in Europe.

2.3.1 SCIANCE key exploitable results

The SCIANCE key project results are the following:

AI in Science Evidence Base

Comprehensive knowledge base consolidating AI in Science and AI for Science state-of-the-art research, good practices registry and European infrastructure mapping

AI in Science Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda

Community-validated strategic framework defining long-term research priorities, cross-domain cooperation strategies, and policy recommendations for AI-enabled scientific breakthroughs

Infrastructure Upgrades Roadmap

Evidence-based scenarios for European AI in Science infrastructure development, including feasibility assessments, investment priorities, and implementation pathways for enhanced resource coordination

RAISE Supporting Pilot Functions

Operational pilot of RAISE coordination mechanisms including the RAISE Digital Hub platform, AIS Summit events, RAISE Academy capacity building programme, and RAISE Secretariat coordination services

The central exploitation objective is to transform SCIANCE outputs into reusable reference assets for the AI in Science community and RAISE stakeholders. Exploitation will therefore be pursued through structured dissemination, open access to relevant outputs, targeted policy and infrastructure engagement, and continued availability through the RAISE Digital Hub.

Scientific and technical sustainability will be supported by making relevant reports, documents, training materials and methodologies openly accessible via the RAISE Digital Hub, ensuring their reusability by research communities beyond the project duration. Outputs will align with FAIR principles, enabling interoperability with EOSC, EuroHPC, AI Factories and other relevant European infrastructures and initiatives. The AI in Science Evidence Base will be curated as a living knowledge base, expandable with additional good practices, mappings and case studies gathered via the

Digital Hub, so that it can serve as a reference point for both researchers and infrastructures beyond the project lifecycle.

Policy and strategic sustainability will be supported by positioning the AI in Science SRIA as a living reference document beyond SCIANCE, designed to be maintained and regularly updated under the RAISE Secretariat. Policy briefs and recommendations will feed into European and national research strategies, supporting the embedding of SRIA priorities in future funding calls and infrastructure investments. The roadmap will be positioned as an actionable planning tool for policymakers and funders, with exploitation pathways through integration into national strategies, ESFRI roadmaps and future European Commission work programmes.

2.3.2 RAISE Secretariat

The RAISE Secretariat will function as the main sustainability pillar for SCIANCE, ensuring continuity of its activities and outputs, including the RAISE Digital Hub, RAISE Academy, SRIA and roadmap. During the project, the Secretariat will pilot the coordination functions required for RAISE, including stakeholder engagement, partnership building, communication support, and alignment with relevant European initiatives such as EOSC, EuroHPC JU, ESFRI, AI Factories, AI networks, and other AI in Science stakeholders.

Hosted by ESF, the Secretariat will be guided by RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference (Deliverable D8.2) co-developed in consultation with the European Commission and RAISE stakeholders. The Terms of Reference provide the operational framework for the Secretariat pilot, defining its scope, roles, responsibilities, processes and rules during the SCIANCE project.

To secure long-term sustainability, the Secretariat will explore operational interfaces with funding organisations, infrastructures and European initiatives, as well as potential governance, hosting, funding and operational models for a long-term RAISE initiative. In this way, SCIANCE will lay the operational and strategic foundations for RAISE by testing and refining the practical elements needed for a durable European coordination framework for AI-enabled science: a shared digital access point, recurring community and policy engagement through AIS Summits, capacity-building activities through the RAISE Academy, and structured stakeholder partnerships.

The RAISE supporting pilot functions will be designed as sustainable mechanisms rather than stand-alone project activities. The Secretariat will support their continuation by contributing to the maintenance and use of the RAISE Digital Hub, enabling access to reusable RAISE Academy training materials, supporting the AIS Summit event format for annual consultation and stakeholder engagement, and coordinating with ongoing initiatives. Partner institutions will also support uptake by integrating SCIANCE results into their own networks and strategic agendas, while synergies with related Horizon Europe projects and infrastructures will sustain momentum through joint dissemination, interoperability activities and shared resources.

At the end of the SCIANCE project, transferable assets (e.g., branding materials, documentation, digital tools) will be placed under secure custodianship with the host of the RAISE Secretariat, pending a decision by the European Commission on the future governance structure of RAISE. Non-transferable assets, including third-party components and jointly owned materials, will be safeguarded through a stewardship framework that ensures continued access and maintenance for RAISE. Should the European Commission establish or designate a legal entity for RAISE, transferable assets will be assigned to that entity. If no such entity is established, the European Commission will determine the appropriate long-term stewardship arrangement.

2.3.3 RAISE Sustainability and Exploitation Plan

The RAISE Secretariat will develop the Sustainability and Exploitation Plan (Deliverable D9.1) to operationalise the transition from SCIANCE pilot activities towards sustainable RAISE structures. It will define operational scenarios for the continuation of Secretariat pilot functions beyond the project lifetime, covering governance options, partnership mechanisms, custodianship of outputs, access and reuse arrangements, and potential funding models. It will also draw on evidence generated through this RAISE pilot project to identify which elements should be continued, adapted, or scaled within the future operational framework for RAISE.

In doing so, the Sustainability and Exploitation Plan will support the transition from the SCIANCE pilot coordination project towards a practical blueprint for the long-term sustainability of RAISE and the wider European AI in Science ecosystem, while preserving the knowledge, relationships, stakeholder engagement processes, and consultation mechanisms developed during the project.

3 Stakeholder Mapping & Engagement

This part provides a simplified and operational framework for engaging the communities that will contribute to the SCIANCE SRIA, the AI in Science Roadmap, and the future RAISE ecosystem. Its purpose is to clarify who should be engaged, why their input is needed, how they will contribute, through which channels, and how their feedback will be integrated into SCIANCE outputs.

The strategy responds to the complexity of the AI in Science stakeholder landscape by using a clear and consistent engagement logic. Rather than multiplying overlapping engagement categories, the document organises stakeholder participation around a small number of coordinated processes linked to the SCIANCE work plan.

The core engagement methodology is:

Evidence and landscape phase – WP1: SCIANCE collects and organises the state of the art, good practices, infrastructure and initiative mappings, and landscape evidence. AISWG experts may review and contribute to this evidence where relevant.

Co-creation and community feedback phase – WP2 / WP3: Draft scientific, AI for Science, infrastructure, and cooperation priorities are developed through domain-specific, transversal, interdisciplinary, and infrastructure-focused workshops. AISWG experts contribute as a structured expert layer. Wider community feedback is then collected through the RAISE Digital Hub's online consultations, and AIS Summit-linked sessions.

Review, integration and strategic alignment phase – WP5: Community feedback is reviewed, summarised and integrated into the SRIA through structured AISWG review and consensus-building moments. In parallel, targeted feedback from relevant initiatives, policy actors, infrastructures, industry and advisory bodies supports strategic alignment with European and national priorities.

A similar logic applies to the AI in Science Roadmap. WP3 identifies infrastructure gaps, upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms through expert and stakeholder input, while WP4 assesses feasibility and supports roadmap development. These outputs are then validated and aligned through WP5 and broader stakeholder consultation. The strategy uses consistent terminology throughout. AISWG is used for the AI in Science Working Groups; AIS Summits for the key ecosystem events; RAISE Digital Hub for the engagement and consultation layer; and RAISE Secretariat for the pilot coordination and continuity support function. Terms such as "WG/EG", "thematic cluster steering bodies" or vague "community sessions" are avoided unless clearly defined.

The strategy distinguishes between different roles in the engagement process. AISWGs provide structured expert input, review and consensus-building, but they are not responsible for operational engagement management, communication campaigns or final project decisions. The SAB provides high-level, non-binding strategic advice and alignment support, but does not approve deliverables. WP/task leaders, WP8/9 and the RAISE Secretariat support coordination, documentation, communication, consultation design and continuity.

The stakeholder groups covered are:

- Research Communities across disciplines
- AI Experts & AI Researchers
- Research Infrastructures, E-Infrastructures & Scientific Facilities
- Policy Makers & Funding Organisations
- Civil Society
- Industry & Innovation Actors
- AISWGs as a key expert co-creation interface
- The SCIANCE Strategic Advisory Board as a strategic advisory interface

For each stakeholder group, the strategy defines the expected contribution, relevant SRIA focus areas, engagement activities, Digital Hub role, expected outputs, timeline, success metrics, risks and transition to RAISE. The intention is not to create a rigid engagement plan, but a clear and usable framework that partners can apply consistently while allowing adjustments during implementation. The RAISE Digital Hub is central to this approach and is therefore treated as an engagement layer, not only as a content repository.

The final objective of this strategy is to make stakeholder engagement simple, traceable and useful: simple enough for partners and external contributors to understand; traceable enough to show how input is collected and used; and useful enough to support credible, community-informed and strategically aligned SCIANCE outputs.

How Engagement Strategy & Stakeholder Mapping Works				
Step	Purpose	Main activities	Main actors	Output
Evidence & landscape	Build the knowledge base	WP1 state-of-the-art review, landscape analysis, good-practice registry	WP1, AISWG experts where relevant, research communities, infrastructures, AI experts	Evidence base, good practices, landscape mapping
Co-create draft priorities	Develop draft SRIA and roadmap inputs	WP2 workshops for scientific and AI for Science priorities; WP3 workshops for infrastructure gaps, scenarios and cooperation mechanisms	AISWG experts, research communities, AI experts, infrastructures	Draft priorities, infrastructure gaps, cooperation options
Collect community feedback	Broaden and test the draft priorities	RAISE Digital Hub consultations, AIS Summit-linked feedback, targeted consultations	Wider community, AISWG experts, policy, industry, civil society, infrastructures	Consultation summaries
Review and integrate feedback	Refine SRIA and roadmap	AISWG review / online consensus meetings; WP/task leader synthesis	AISWGs, WP leads, RAISE Secretariat support	Revised SRIA and roadmap inputs
Strategic alignment	Align with European initiatives and policy bodies	WP5 targeted feedback with key stakeholders	Policy actors, funders, infrastructures, SAB, strategic initiatives	Final SRIA and roadmap alignment

Engagement types & flows		
Engagement flow	What it means	Where it happens
Evidence input and review	Stakeholders contribute to the state of the art ,landscape analysis and good-practice registry .AISWG experts may review and complement WP1 evidence.	WP1 ,RAISE Digital Hub
Co-creation and validation	AISWG experts and relevant stakeholders help develop and review scientific priorities ,AI for Science priorities , infrastructure gaps ,upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms.	WP2 workshops ,WP3 workshops ,AISWG meetings
Consultation and strategic alignment	Wider communities provide feedback; key bodies and initiatives help align the SRIA and roadmap with European and national priorities.	RAISE Digital Hub ,AIS Summits ,WP5 targeted consultations ,SAB input

AISWG Role in Co-Creation of Draft SRIA Priorities				
Phase	What happens inside AISWGs	Who does what	Role of the RAISE Digital Hub	Output
Preparation before workshops	AISWG experts receive a focused briefing based on WP1 evidence, good practices and landscape analysis. They review the material and identify initial scientific challenges, AI for Science opportunities, gaps and dependencies.	WP2 and WP3 task leads prepare the briefing, guiding questions and workshop framing. WP2 focuses on scientific and AI for Science priorities, while WP3 frames infrastructure gaps, upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms. AISWG members provide initial expert input. AISWG co-chairs help focus the discussion. WP8/9 and the RAISE Secretariat support coordination and documentation.	Hosts briefing materials, guiding questions, background evidence and restricted AISWG discussion/input spaces where needed.	Initial expert input, refined questions and candidate priority areas.
Co-creation during workshops	AISWG experts participate in domain, transversal or interdisciplinary WP2 workshops. Draft priorities are discussed, clustered and prioritised.	WP2 leads facilitate workshops. AISWG experts contribute scientific and technical expertise. Relevant stakeholders contribute where appropriate.	Provides access to agendas, templates, workshop materials and shared documentation.	Draft scientific priorities, AI for Science priorities and interdisciplinary cooperation needs.
Review after workshops	AISWGs review workshop synthesis notes or priority fiches. They check accuracy, identify consensus, flag divergent views and note cross-AISWG dependencies.	WP2/task leads prepare synthesis. AISWG members review and comment. Co-chairs support consensus-building. WP8/9 / Secretariat supports traceability.	Hosts synthesis notes, review templates, feedback forms and discussion threads; records comments and revisions.	Reviewed priorities, consensus points, open issues, dissenting views and cross-WG dependencies.
Wider community feedback	Reviewed draft priorities are opened to broader consultation beyond the AISWGs. AISWG experts may help interpret feedback but do not manage the consultation.	WP8/9 / RAISE Secretariat coordinates consultation. Broader community provides input. AISWGs may review consultation summaries.	Hosts open or targeted consultations, surveys, feedback forms, Living SRIA threads and public summaries.	Community feedback summary and evidence of broader validation.
Integration into SRIA	AISWG input and community feedback are considered for integration into SRIA outputs. Final decisions remain with the consortium.	WP2/WP5 task leads integrate inputs into deliverables. AISWGs provide expert interpretation where needed. Consortium governance remains responsible for final decisions.	Archives consultation summaries and shows how feedback was considered, supporting traceability across WP1-WP5.	Inputs to D2.1, D2.2, D2.3 and later SRIA integration under D5.1.

3.1 Key Strategic Parties

SCIANCE relies on two dedicated strategic interfaces to support the development, review and alignment of the SRIA and the AI in Science Roadmap: the AISWGs and the SCIANCE SAB. The AISWGs provide the core expert co-creation and review layer. They bring together selected experts from scientific communities, AI research, research infrastructures, industry, Open Science and related stakeholder groups. Their role is to contribute focused expertise to the identification of scientific priorities, AI for Science research and innovation priorities, infrastructure needs, cooperation mechanisms and draft SRIA / roadmap outputs. AISWG participation is structured, time-bound and supported by WP/task leaders, co-chairs, the RAISE Secretariat and the RAISE Digital Hub. The SAB provides high-level strategic advice and alignment support. It helps ensure that SCIANCE outputs are relevant to the wider European AI in Science ecosystem, Member State priorities, research infrastructure roadmaps, policy frameworks and strategic initiatives. The SAB acts in an advisory, non-binding capacity and does not approve deliverables or manage stakeholder engagement activities.

Together, AISWGs and the SAB ensure that SCIANCE combines bottom-up expert input with high-level strategic alignment. AISWGs support the scientific and technical credibility of the SRIA and roadmap, while the SAB supports their strategic relevance, positioning and uptake potential. Operational coordination, synthesis, communication and final project decisions remain the responsibility of the SCIANCE consortium, supported by WP/task leaders, WP8/9 and the RAISE Secretariat.

3.1.1 AI In Science Working Groups (AISWG)

AI in Science Working Groups / AISWG	
WHO	AI in Science Working Group experts selected through an open Call for Expression of Interest and nominations. AISWGs bring together domain scientists, AI researchers, industry experts, Open Science advocates, representatives of European initiatives and infrastructures, citizen scientists, engineers, research enablers, data/model repository owners and resource providers. The AISWG structure covers 10 thematic groups: five scientific pilot areas and five cross-cutting AI-related topics.
WHY ENGAGE	AISWGs are the core expert co-creation and validation layer of SCIANCE. They provide structured expert input to ensure that the SRIA reflects scientific community needs, AI research priorities, infrastructure requirements, and cross-domain cooperation opportunities. Their role is to support the identification, prioritisation and review of AI in Science and AI for Science priorities, while the consortium remains responsible for final deliverables and decisions.
WHAT WE NEED	Focused expert input on scientific challenges, AI-enabled opportunities, AI for Science methods, infrastructure upgrade requirements, cooperation mechanisms, trust, reproducibility, data, skills, Open Science and frugal AI. AISWG experts may provide use cases, evidence, good-practice examples, resources or data where relevant. However, their contribution should remain structured and time-bound: workshops, selected online meetings, asynchronous review and consultation feedback, not continuous drafting or platform management. Selection criteria: Expertise, Contribution, Diversity, Coverage
AISWG STRUCTURE	Domain-specific AISWGs: Astronomy & Fundamental Physics; Materials Science; Life Sciences; Earth Sciences; Social Sciences & Humanities. Cross-cutting AISWGs: AI Research & Experimental Design; Data Science & Advanced Analytics; Open Science & Trustworthy AI; AI & Computing Infrastructures; Industry, Innovation & Frugal AI.
SRIA / ROADMAP FOCUS	Domain AISWGs support the identification of long-term scientific research challenges and domain-specific AI opportunities. Cross-cutting AISWGs support AI methods, data, infrastructures, Open Science, trust, frugal AI, innovation, and interdisciplinary cooperation. Across the process, AISWGs provide expert input to SRIA priorities, infrastructure upgrade requirements and cooperation mechanisms.
KEY QUESTIONS	What are the most relevant AI-enabled scientific challenges in each domain where AI can make a difference? Which AI methods and research workflows have cross-domain potential? What data, infrastructure, compute, governance, or skills requirements are needed? Which priorities are sufficiently mature and evidence-based for the SRIA? What consultation feedback should be integrated, refined, or flagged as divergent? What cross-AISWG dependencies need coordination?

	<p>What are the most relevant scientific challenges in each domain where AI can make a substantial difference? Which AI methods, models, tools or research workflows have potential to be reused, adapted or scaled across more than one scientific pilot area? Where are the main opportunities to develop new AI models, tools, workflows or experimental approaches, and where would better integration or uptake of existing AI tools be sufficient? What is needed to better integrate AI into scientific practice, including data readiness, infrastructure, compute, governance, interoperability, skills, trust, reproducibility and Open Science requirements? Which priorities are sufficiently mature, evidence-based and feasible for inclusion in the SRIA? What consultation feedback should be integrated, refined or flagged as divergent? What dependencies between domain-specific and cross-cutting AISWGs need coordination?</p>
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	<p>CO-CREATE / REVIEW / VALIDATE. AISWGs act in an advisory capacity. They provide expert input, review outputs, and support consensus-building where possible. Dissenting views may be recorded where relevant. Final decisions on project deliverables remain the responsibility of the SCIANCE consortium, while operational coordination, documentation, stakeholder engagement support, and process management are supported by the RAISE Secretariat and relevant WP/task leaders.</p>
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	<p>Participation in co-creation workshops; online AISWG meetings at least twice per year; asynchronous review of relevant outputs; contribution to Digital Hub consultations where relevant; review of consultation summaries; participation in consensus-building moments; selected participation in AIS Summit sessions where feasible; provision of additional input, insights, resources or data when needed and realistic.</p>
EXPECTED COMMITMENT	<p>Participation is voluntary. Each AISWG expert is expected to contribute through at least one in-person workshop during the project, supported at least partially for travel where applicable, plus online meetings and asynchronous feedback when requested. This should be presented as a realistic expert contribution model, not as a standing workload.</p>
AISWG co-chairs	<p>One SCIANCE consortium co-chair and one appointed expert co-chair per AISWG, with possible additional SCIANCE co-chairing for complex groups.</p>
ROLE OF AISWG CO-CHAIRS	<p>AISWG co-chairs facilitate strategic discussion within their group and coordinate with other AISWG co-chairs to align recommendations on cross-cutting topics. Each AISWG is co-chaired by a SCIANCE consortium member and one expert appointed from the AISWG members; additional SCIANCE co-chairing may be added where disciplinary coverage requires it.</p>
ROLE OF RAISE SECRETARIAT / CONSORTIUM SUPPORT	<p>The RAISE Secretariat supports AISWG activities by facilitating meeting organisation, access to documentation, balanced representation, distribution of effort and continuity across working groups. WP/task leaders and the consortium remain responsible for synthesis, deliverable preparation, quality assurance and final decisions. This is essential to avoid overloading AISWG experts.</p>
DIGITAL HUB ROLE	<p>The RAISE Digital Hub supports AISWG work through structured access to documents, consultation materials, feedback tools, thematic discussion spaces and summaries. It should make expert review easier by organising inputs and preserving traceability. It should not imply that AISWG experts must continuously monitor, moderate or manage the platform. Dedicated or restricted AISWG spaces may be used where draft materials are confidential. Additional engagement activities are related to: Co-creation workshops, AISWG online meetings, RAISE Digital Hub thematic or restricted spaces, structured consultation forms/surveys, targeted email updates or digests, AIS Summit-linked sessions, and summaries prepared by WP/task leads, rapporteurs or Secretariat support.</p>
CONFIDENTIALITY / DATA PROTECTION	<p>AISWG members treat non-public documents, draft materials and discussions as confidential. Personal data is processed according to EU and national legislation. The composition of the AISWGs will be public, and contributions from experts will be acknowledged in the SCIANCE communications activities, SRIA, roadmap and other project documents where relevant.</p>
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	<p>Expert input for D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3; infrastructure and cooperation input for D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3 where relevant; feedback on WP1 evidence and good-practice outputs where relevant; review of consultation summaries; input to SRIA and roadmap validation; identification of cross-domain dependencies, tensions or gaps requiring WP-level coordination.</p>

TIMELINE	<p>M1–M10 / until AISWG establishment: AISWG preparation, Call for Expression of Interest, selection, onboarding and alignment with WP1 evidence, landscape analysis and good-practice outputs. The AISWGs are expected to become operational following the open call and selection process, with D6.3 indicating operation from April 2026 to June 2028.</p> <p>M8–M20: Main co-creation phase through WP2 and WP3 workshops, online AISWG meetings, structured Digital Hub consultations and AIS Summit-linked feedback. AISWG experts contribute to the identification, review and prioritisation of scientific challenges, AI for Science priorities, infrastructure requirements and cooperation mechanisms.</p> <p>M19–M30: Validation and consolidation phase through WP4/WP5. AISWGs provide focused review of consultation feedback, SRIA and roadmap materials, and contribute expert input to final consensus-building where relevant. Final deliverable decisions remain with the SCIANCE consortium.</p>
RISKS & MITIGATION	<p>Risk: expert fatigue, unclear expectations, low participation, uneven representation, overload from too many requests, or confusion between advisory and operational roles.</p> <p>Mitigation: use structured and time-bound requests; provide clear agendas and review templates; rely on WP/task leaders, co-chairs and Secretariat support for synthesis and coordination; use flexible participation formats; monitor participation and adjust membership where needed; record dissenting views rather than forcing artificial consensus. This is also consistent with the Project Handbook for risk mitigation for low AISWG participation, which recommends early engagement, flexible participation models, monitoring and membership adjustment if needed.</p>
RELATION TO SAB	<p>AISWGs provide expert community input and technical/scientific validation. The SAB provides high-level strategic, non-binding advice on project outputs, alignment with European and Member State priorities, and connections to wider initiatives. SAB input is collected through a dedicated consultation process coordinated by the SCIANCE Coordinator, and recommendations are reviewed by the Management Committee.</p>
TRANSITION TO RAISE / HUB DEVELOPMENT	<p>AISWG outputs, consultation summaries and thematic discussion records will inform the development of future RAISE community structures through the RAISE Digital Hub. The Hub should preserve the knowledge generated by AISWGs and support future consultation cycles without assuming that current AISWG members automatically take on long-term operational roles.</p> <p>Formal long-term governance, access rights, moderation responsibilities, expert commitments, partnership mechanisms and sustainability arrangements will be defined through the RAISE Hub operational model, aligned with D8.2 RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference, and further elaborated in D9.1 Sustainability and Exploitation Plan.</p>

3.1.2 SCIANCE Strategic Advisory Board (SAB)

STRATEGIC ADVISORY BOARD	
WHO	<p>The SCIANCE Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) is composed of a limited number of high-level external advisors or representatives able to provide strategic insight, approximately 9, from European and international organisations and initiatives relevant to AI in Science. Intended profiles include representatives or experts linked to research infrastructures, AI initiatives, AI industry, EOSC/data spaces, ESFRI roadmaps, international AI in Science efforts, ERA Action on AI in Science, and GenAI4EU / Science for AI coordination. The SAB should ensure balanced representation across research, infrastructure, policy, industry, and strategic ecosystem perspectives.</p>
WHY ENGAGE	<p>The SAB provides high-level, external strategic advice to strengthen the scientific relevance, strategic alignment, credibility and uptake potential of SCIANCE outputs. It helps ensure that the SRIA, roadmap, infrastructure scenarios, cooperation mechanisms and sustainability pathways remain aligned with European and Member State priorities, existing roadmaps, strategic initiatives and the wider AI in Science ecosystem.</p>
WHAT WE NEED	<p>Strategic feedback on the relevance, robustness and feasibility of project outputs; advice on alignment with European and Member State priorities; identification of strategic opportunities, risks and gaps; suggestions for stakeholder engagement and positioning; connections to relevant initiatives, infrastructures, networks and events; input on how SCIANCE outputs can support uptake, endorsement and long-term sustainability.</p>

ROLE IN ENGAGEMENT	The SAB acts as a strategic advisory and alignment layer, not as an operational engagement body. Its role is to provide non-binding advice, targeted feedback, strategic positioning, network intelligence and high-level recommendations. SAB input is considered by the SCIANCE Management Committee and consortium; final decisions on deliverables and project direction remain with the consortium governance structures.
MAIN AREAS OF FEEDBACK	State-of-the-art reviews and landscape analysis; good-practice registry; long-term scientific research challenges; AI for Science research and innovation priorities; interdisciplinary cooperation priorities; infrastructure upgrade scenarios; cooperation framework; feasibility assessment; implementation roadmap; AI in Science SRIA; sustainability pathways and RAISE positioning.
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	ADVISE / STRATEGICALLY ALIGN. The SAB provides high-level guidance and targeted feedback at key moments. Its role is advisory, facultative and non-binding. SAB members are not expected to participate in continuous co-creation, routine consultations, platform moderation, deliverable drafting, or operational stakeholder engagement.
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	Participation in at least two SAB meetings during the project, for example around mid-term and prior to final reporting; contribution to dedicated consultation processes coordinated by the SCIANCE Coordinator; targeted review of selected outputs or strategic questions; participation in relevant AIS Summit sessions where feasible; participation as observers in General Assembly meetings where appropriate; individual written contributions if meetings cannot be arranged.
RELATION TO AISWGs	AISWGs provide expert community input, co-creation and technical/scientific review across domains and cross-cutting topics. The SAB provides high-level strategic advice, external alignment and ecosystem positioning. The two bodies are complementary but should not be given overlapping operational responsibilities. AISWG input supports bottom-up expert legitimacy; SAB input supports strategic relevance and alignment with wider European initiatives.
RELATION TO CONSORTIUM GOVERNANCE	The SAB is appointed and steered by the General Assembly. SAB consultation processes are coordinated by the SCIANCE Coordinator / ESF under the relevant coordination tasks. SAB feedback and recommendations are advisory and non-binding; they are reviewed and considered by the SCIANCE Management Committee and, where relevant, by the responsible WP leads for integration into project outputs. The SAB does not approve deliverables or make binding project decisions.
DIGITAL HUB ROLE	The RAISE Digital Hub may provide SAB members with access to public outputs, consultation summaries, SRIA/roadmap materials and relevant engagement evidence. Restricted access to draft materials may be provided where appropriate, subject to confidentiality and access rules. The Hub should support transparency and traceability of consultation results, but SAB engagement itself remains coordinated through dedicated advisory processes led by the SCIANCE Coordinator. RAISE Secretariat support for documentation and continuity; RAISE Digital Hub access to relevant public or restricted materials where appropriate.
COMMUNICATION ROLE	SAB members may support visibility and uptake by relaying selected SCIANCE activities, outputs or consultation opportunities through their professional networks and initiatives where appropriate. However, communication planning, dissemination campaigns and stakeholder engagement operations remain the responsibility of the consortium, especially WP8/9 and the RAISE Secretariat pilot.
EXPECTED CONTRIBUTIONS	Strategic advice on project outputs; feedback on selected deliverables and synthesis documents; identification of risks, opportunities and strategic gaps; advice on alignment with European and Member State priorities; network introductions and suggestions for stakeholder engagement; support for recognition and uptake of SCIANCE outputs where feasible.
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	SAB meeting minutes; written feedback or recommendations where relevant; strategic advice incorporated into Management Committee and WP-level discussions; documented input on key outputs such as the SRIA, roadmap, infrastructure scenarios, cooperation mechanisms, and sustainability pathways; identification of relevant initiatives, networks, and events for alignment.
TIMELINE	M1-M10 / SAB establishment and orientation: SAB appointment and onboarding, with initial strategic orientation once members are confirmed. Where timing allows and specific questions are raised by the consortium, SAB members may provide targeted input on knowledge consolidation, landscape analysis, and good-practice framing.

	<p>M8–M20 / Mid-term strategic feedback: SAB provides strategic feedback on emerging research priorities, infrastructure gaps, cooperation mechanisms, and alignment with wider European and Member State priorities. This phase may include the first formal SAB meeting around mid-term, participation in relevant AIS Summit sessions, and/or written feedback if a meeting is not feasible.</p> <p>M19–M30 / Final strategic review: SAB provides a strategic review of the SRIA, roadmap, feasibility assessment, and sustainability pathways before final reporting and dissemination. This phase should include the second formal SAB meeting prior to final reporting, with additional targeted feedback as needed. SAB advice remains non-binding and is considered by the SCIANCE Management Committee and relevant WP leads.</p>
RISKS & MITIGATION	<p>Risk: limited availability of high-level experts, unclear expectations, overlap with AISWG roles, or overloading SAB members with too many review requests.</p> <p>Mitigation: use focused and well-prepared advisory requests; provide short briefing notes and clear questions; allow written feedback when meetings are not feasible; ensure each SAB member has a deputy where possible; keep the SAB role strategic and non-operational; separate SAB advice from AISWG co-creation.</p>
CONFIDENTIALITY / DATA PROTECTION	<p>SAB members may receive non-public or draft materials and should treat them as confidential where required. Any personal data or engagement records are handled in line with EU and national data protection requirements and SCIANCE data management procedures.</p>
TRANSITION TO RAISE / HUB DEVELOPMENT	<p>SAB insights, strategic relationships and lessons learned may inform future RAISE advisory or alignment mechanisms. The RAISE Digital Hub can preserve public outputs, consultation summaries and strategic alignment materials for continuity. Any formal continuation of SAB functions, governance roles, access rights or advisory mechanisms under RAISE will be defined separately in the RAISE Hub operational model and related governance documents.</p>

3.1.3 Research Communities

Research communities	
WHO	<p>Universities, research institutions, individual researchers from early-career to senior level, research groups, doctoral schools, learned societies, scientific networks, disciplinary associations, AI-in-science research groups, and interdisciplinary research centres across the five pilot scientific areas: Astronomy & Physics, Materials Science, Earth Sciences, Life Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities. This group also includes researchers contributing to cross-cutting AI for Science themes and scientific workflows.</p>
WHY ENGAGE	<p>Research communities are the primary source of bottom-up, science-led priorities for the SRIA. They provide domain expertise, identify AI-enabled scientific challenges, validate whether proposed priorities reflect real research needs, contribute evidence and good practices, and help ensure that the SRIA is scientifically credible, community-owned, and grounded in actual research practice.</p>
WHAT WE NEED	<p>Input on long-term scientific challenges where AI can enable breakthroughs; input on AI for Science methods and tools across the research lifecycle; identification of research gaps, infrastructure needs, skills gaps, and trust/reproducibility issues; contribution of good-practice cases for the AI-enabled Science registry; validation of draft priorities through AISWGs, workshops, Digital Hub consultations, and AIS Summit feedback.</p>
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	<p>Primary: Scientific Research Challenges; AI for Science Research & Innovation Priorities; Trustworthy, Responsible and Reproducible AI; Skills, Roles & Interdisciplinary Research Culture.</p> <p>Secondary / needs-based: Data & Open Science; Infrastructure & Platforms, especially where research communities identify data, compute, interoperability, access, skills or infrastructure bottlenecks affecting scientific practice.</p>
KEY QUESTIONS	<p>Which scientific challenges are most transformed by AI? Where can AI make a meaningful difference for scientific breakthroughs? What AI methods and tools are needed across the research lifecycle? What skills, roles, and incentives are required? How should AI-enabled scientific results be validated, interpreted, reproduced, and trusted? What good practices already exist and under which conditions do they work? What regulatory, governance and ethical issues must the SRIA address?</p>

ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	<p>INVOLVE → CO-CREATE. Research communities contribute to SCIANCE through selected participation in AISWGs, domain-specific, transversal and interdisciplinary workshops, RAISE Digital Hub consultations, AIS Summit-linked feedback moments, and SRIA / roadmap validation cycles. AISWG participation follows transparent selection criteria, including relevant expertise, availability to contribute, disciplinary diversity, balanced representation across EU Member States and Associated Countries, gender balance, career-stage representation, and coverage across stakeholder communities.</p>
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	<p>Research communities will contribute to WP1 landscape analysis, state-of-the-art evidence collection and good-practice identification; participate in WP2 domain-specific, transversal and interdisciplinary co-creation workshops; provide input to WP3 infrastructure gap and cooperation consultations where scientific practice depends on data, compute, access, skills or governance conditions; engage through RAISE Digital Hub thematic forums, surveys and feedback mechanisms; contribute to AIS Summit-linked feedback and consultation sessions; and participate in WP5 SRIA and roadmap consultation, validation and endorsement processes.</p>
RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	<p>Access evolving outputs; respond to consultations; contribute to thematic discussions; submit or validate good practices; follow summaries of how community input informs SRIA and roadmap development. The Hub supports engagement through surveys, feedback collection, thematic forums, and structured consultation spaces. Linked with: AIS Summit-linked sessions; scientific societies and disciplinary networks; institutional mailing lists and newsletters; partner networks; research conferences and community events; targeted updates coordinated by WP8/9 with support from the RAISE Secretariat.</p>
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	<p>Contributions to the WP1 evidence base and good-practice registry; inputs to D2.1 Long-term scientific research challenges, D2.2 AI for Science research and innovation priorities, and D2.3 Interdisciplinary AI cooperation priorities; user-community input to D3.1 Infrastructure gap analysis, and, where relevant, to D3.2 Infrastructure upgrade scenarios and D3.3 AI in Science Cooperation framework; feedback on the draft SRIA (D5.1) and AI in Science Roadmap (D4.2); validation, consultation and uptake feedback supporting final SRIA and roadmap consolidation.</p>
TIMELINE	<p>M1–M10: Identification and mobilisation of relevant research communities; contribution to WP1 state-of-the-art evidence, landscape analysis and good-practice input; preparation and recruitment of selected experts for AISWG and workshop participation. M8–M20: Active co-creation through WP2 domain-specific, transversal and interdisciplinary workshops, and needs-based input to WP3 infrastructure gap, scenario and cooperation consultations where scientific practice depends on data, compute, access, skills or governance conditions. M19–M30: Participation in SRIA and roadmap consultation and validation processes, including review of draft outputs, feedback through the RAISE Digital Hub and AIS Summit-linked activities, and contribution to uptake and continuity discussions supported by the RAISE Secretariat and Digital Hub.</p>
RISKS & MITIGATION	<p>Risk: low participation, consultation fatigue, AI hype, imbalance across domains or seniority levels. Mitigation: targeted invitations through partner and society networks; short and focused consultations; co-location with major scientific events; use of concrete cases and good practices; transparent recognition of contributions.</p>
COMMUNICATION ROLE	<p>Research communities may help amplify SCIANCE/RAISE calls, consultations, outputs and good-practice opportunities through their scientific networks, societies, institutions and events. Communication remains coordinated by WP8/9, with support from the RAISE Secretariat, while research communities strengthen visibility, credibility and outreach within their own domains.</p>

3.1.4 AI Experts & AI Researchers

AI experts & AI researchers	
WHO	AI researchers and technology experts from academia, research organisations, industry R&D, AI labs, centres of excellence, national AI initiatives, and AI4Science communities. This includes machine learning researchers, computer scientists, data scientists, AI engineers, generative AI and foundation model experts, explainable and trustworthy AI specialists, NLP, computer vision and multimodal AI experts, AI safety and ethics researchers, and domain scientists developing or applying advanced AI methods.
WHY ENGAGE	AI experts provide the technical expertise needed to connect scientific challenges with feasible AI methods, tools, and infrastructures. They help ensure that the SRIA is grounded in state-of-the-art AI capabilities and limitations, supports trustworthy and frugal AI, and identifies where AI can genuinely transform scientific discovery and research workflows.
WHAT WE NEED	Input on emerging AI methods, tools, and applications relevant to science; assessment of technical feasibility and limitations; guidance on benchmarking, validation, explainability, robustness, and reproducibility; input on foundation models, scientific LLMs, multimodal AI, human-centric AI, frugal AI, and trustworthy AI; identification of compute, data, platform and interoperability requirements; contribution of technical good practices and lessons learned from AI in Science initiatives.
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	Primary: AI for Science R&I Priorities; Scientific Priorities where AI enables new discovery; Trust & Integrity; Infrastructure & Platforms. Secondary: Data & Open Science; Skills & Culture; Governance & Legal, especially where technical choices affect ethics, compliance, transparency, and sustainability.
KEY QUESTIONS	<p>Which AI methods are most relevant for scientific discovery across domains? How do foundation models, scientific LLMs, multimodal AI, lab automation and human-in-the-loop systems change research practice? What technical standards are needed for validation, benchmarking, explainability, and reproducibility? What data, compute, and platform requirements are needed for scalable AI in Science? How can AI methods remain trustworthy, human-centric, and energy-efficient?</p> <p>Which AI methods, models, tools and systems are most relevant for scientific discovery and research workflows across the SCIANCE pilot domains? How can foundation models, scientific LLMs, multimodal AI, human-in-the-loop systems, autonomous experimentation and AI-assisted research workflows change research practice, and how does this differ by domain? Where are the biggest opportunities to develop new AI models, tools, workflows or experimental approaches, and where would better adaptation, integration or uptake of existing AI tools be sufficient?</p> <p>What technical and organisational conditions are needed to support responsible AI adoption in research, including benchmarking, validation, explainability, robustness, reproducibility, documentation, transparency, privacy, confidentiality, IPR protection, human oversight and compliance with EU guidance on responsible AI use in research?</p> <p>How can AI systems be integrated in ways that remain trustworthy, human-centric, open, reproducible, frugal and energy-efficient?</p> <p>What training, support structures, governance mechanisms and feedback loops are needed so that researchers can use AI tools responsibly and effectively?</p> <p>Which technical priorities are sufficiently mature, evidence-based, feasible and scalable for inclusion in the SRIA and roadmap? Which priorities require further experimentation, piloting, monitoring or community validation before being recommended?</p> <p>What consultation feedback should be integrated, refined or flagged as divergent? What dependencies between domain-specific AISWGs and cross-cutting AISWGs need coordination?</p>
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	CO-CREATE / REVIEW / VALIDATE. AI experts contribute expert-level input to technical priority-setting, cross-domain AI for Science workshops, AISWG discussions, infrastructure gap analysis where relevant, and expert review of SRIA and roadmap recommendations. Their role should be structured and time-bound, through workshops, AISWG meetings, Digital Hub consultations and asynchronous feedback, rather than open-ended operational work. AISWG participation follows transparent selection criteria, including relevant expertise, availability to contribute, disciplinary diversity, balanced representation across EU Member States and

	Associated Countries, gender balance, career-stage representation, and coverage across stakeholder communities.
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	AI experts contribute to WP1 state-of-the-art review of AI for Science methods, tools and emerging technologies; WP1 landscape analysis and good-practice identification; WP2 domain workshops where AI expertise is needed to connect scientific challenges with feasible methods; WP2 transversal AI for Science workshops; and the WP2 interdisciplinary cooperation workshop where relevant. They may also contribute to WP3 infrastructure gap analysis and scenario consultations where issues concern AI methods, compute, software, data workflows, model repositories, benchmarking or user support. Additional engagement takes place through RAISE Digital Hub thematic forums, surveys and feedback mechanisms, AIS Summit-linked expert sessions, and WP5 SRIA / roadmap consultation through technical review and validation feedback.
RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	AI experts use the RAISE Digital Hub to access evolving SRIA, roadmap, evidence-base and good-practice outputs; respond to technical consultations; contribute to thematic discussions on AI methods, tools, benchmarking, trustworthiness, frugal AI, data workflows and infrastructure needs; and submit or validate relevant AI for Science good practices. The Hub supports structured engagement through surveys, feedback collection, thematic forums and Discourse consultation spaces, while making visible how expert input informs SRIA and roadmap development.
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	Inputs to WP1 AI for Science evidence base and good-practice registry; inputs to D2.1 where AI methods address domain challenges; inputs to D2.2 on AI for Science R&I priorities; inputs to D2.3 on interdisciplinary cooperation and model sharing; input to D3.1 on technical infrastructure gaps; input to D3.2 and D3.3 where AI platforms, compute, data and cooperation mechanisms are relevant; technical feedback on the SRIA and roadmap; validation inputs for D5.1.
TIMELINE	M1–M10: Identification and mobilisation of relevant AI experts; contribution to WP1 AI for Science state-of-the-art review, landscape analysis, and good-practice input; preparation and onboarding of selected AI experts for AISWG and workshop participation. M8–M20: Active co-creation through WP2 transversal AI for Science workshops and relevant domain/interdisciplinary workshops; contribution to WP3 infrastructure gap, scenario and cooperation consultations where issues concern AI methods, compute, software, data workflows, model repositories, benchmarking or technical feasibility; feedback through the RAISE Digital Hub and AIS Summit-linked activities. M19–M30: Technical review and validation feedback on SRIA and roadmap outputs; contribution to final consultation and uptake discussions where technical expertise is relevant; continued connection through the RAISE Digital Hub and Secretariat-supported processes, with any formal long-term roles defined separately in the RAISE Hub operational model and future governance arrangements.
RISKS & MITIGATION	Risk: low participation, consultation fatigue, AI hype, imbalance across domains or seniority levels. Mitigation: targeted invitations through partner and society networks; short and focused consultations; co-location with major scientific events; use of concrete cases and good practices; transparent recognition of contributions.
COMMUNICATION ROLE	AI experts may help amplify SCIANCE/RAISE calls, consultations, technical outputs and good-practice opportunities through AI research networks, centres of excellence, AI4Science communities, conferences and professional channels. Communication remains coordinated by WP8/9, with support from the RAISE Secretariat, while AI experts strengthen technical credibility and outreach within relevant AI communities.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	AI research networks and European AI networks of excellence; AI centres and university AI/CS departments; national AI and AI in Science initiatives; AI4Science communities; partner and AISWG networks; RAISE Digital Hub and Discourse consultation spaces; newsletters, LinkedIn and targeted campaigns coordinated by WP8/9 with support from the RAISE Secretariat; AI, data and AI4Science conferences and workshops, including AIS, International Conference AI for Science, BDVA / EBDVF and ELLIS-related events; EOSC-related channels; and relevant European AI ecosystem initiatives such as ADRA, ELLIS, CAIRNE, AI-on-Demand, AI4EOSC and the GenAI / GenAI4EU Hub.

3.1.5 Research Infrastructures, E-Infrastructures & Scientific Facilities

Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures & scientific facilities	
WHO	<p>Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures, scientific facilities, compute providers, data infrastructures, and national infrastructure actors supporting AI in Science. This includes: ESFRI Research Infrastructures and ERICs across the five pilot domains; European e-infrastructures and Open Science infrastructures such as EGI, GÉANT, OpenAIRE, EOSC-related structures and service providers; HPC and AI compute providers such as EuroHPC JU, EuroHPC hosting entities, AI Factories, national HPC centres and cloud/HPC providers; large-scale scientific facilities such as CERN, ESA, ESO, SKA, EUMETSAT, EMBL, photon/neutron facilities and Copernicus-related infrastructures; and national or regional research infrastructures, including national data centres, university computing consortia, national Open Science platforms, and national AI in Science initiatives.</p> <p>*SCIANCE will build on the existing ESFRI Roadmap, ERIC, EOSC, EuroHPC, AI Factory, and national infrastructure knowledge. The aim is not to remap the European infrastructure landscape from scratch, but to identify AI-relevant data, compute, service, interoperability, access, governance, and skills needs that can inform the SRIA, infrastructure gap analysis, upgrade scenarios, and roadmap development.</p>
WHY ENGAGE	<p>These actors are central to making RAISE operationally feasible. They provide the data, compute, platforms, services, standards, access mechanisms, and user support needed for scalable and trustworthy AI-enabled research. Their involvement ensures that the SRIA and roadmap are grounded in real infrastructure capabilities, aligned with existing infrastructure roadmaps, and responsive to the needs of scientific communities. The proposal explicitly links infrastructures to AI-ready data, computing, governance, skills, upgrade scenarios, and long-term sustainability.</p>
WHAT WE NEED	<p>Input on AI-ready data, compute needs, data access, FAIR compliance, metadata, provenance, interoperability, AAI, service integration, platform requirements, user support, governance, sustainability, and skills gaps. We also need infrastructure use cases, good practices, examples of AI-enabled service provision, feedback on infrastructure bottlenecks, and validation of infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms.</p> <p>Input on AI-ready data, current and projected use of AI-optimised compute and supercomputing resources across scientific fields, data access, FAIR compliance, metadata, provenance, interoperability, AAI, service integration, platform requirements, user support, governance, sustainability, AI Act-related compliance needs and skills gaps. We also need evidence on the extent to which computing resources are currently used by different scientific communities, for which AI-enabled research workflows, how usage varies by field, and how demand is expected to increase as AI adoption, AI Factories and AI-enabled service provision scale. This should include infrastructure use cases, good practices, examples of AI-enabled service provision, feedback on compute and infrastructure bottlenecks, and validation of infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms.</p>
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	<p>Primary: Infrastructure & Platforms; Data & Open Science. Secondary: Governance & Legal; Trust & Integrity; Skills & Culture; Scientific and AI for Science R&I Priorities where scientific challenges depend on infrastructure capabilities.</p>
KEY QUESTIONS	<p>What data, compute, service, and platform capabilities are needed to scale AI in Science? What makes scientific data AI-ready across domains? What are the main gaps in access, interoperability, provenance, metadata, governance, and user support? What federation and service models can avoid fragmentation or lock-in? What infrastructure upgrade scenarios are realistic, sustainable, and aligned with EOSC, EuroHPC JU, ESFRI, AI Factories and national infrastructures? What good practices already exist in AI-enabled infrastructure support?</p>
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	<p>INVOLVE → CO-CREATE. Infrastructure actors are deeply involved in defining requirements, identifying gaps, co-designing upgrade scenarios, validating feasibility, and ensuring the roadmap is operationally realistic. Their role is strongest in WP3 and WP4, while they also contribute to WP1 evidence, WP2 where infrastructure enables scientific priorities, and WP5 strategic alignment.</p>

ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	<p>WP1 infrastructure mapping and good-practice identification; WP2 domain and transversal workshops where infrastructure capabilities shape research priorities; WP3 infrastructure gap analysis; WP3 co-design of infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms; WP4 feasibility assessment; WP5 SRIA and roadmap validation; RAISE Digital Hub consultations, thematic forums, surveys and feedback mechanisms; AIS Summit infrastructure, roadmap and strategic alignment sessions.</p> <p>* Infrastructure engagement is directly linked to WP1/D1.4–D1.5, WP3/D3.1–D3.3, and WP4/D4.1–D4.2. & Their input also supports WP5/D5.1 where infrastructure requirements need to be reflected in the SRIA and aligned with European initiatives and policy frameworks.</p>
RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	<p>Access landscape mapping, good-practice resources, infrastructure-related outputs, SRIA drafts and roadmap materials; respond to targeted infrastructure consultations; contribute to thematic discussions on AI-ready data, compute, interoperability, access, services, and governance; submit or validate infrastructure-related good practices; follow summaries of how infrastructure input informs roadmap and SRIA development. The Hub supports structured engagement through surveys, feedback collection, thematic forums and consultation spaces. Additional links: Detailed governance, access rights, partnership mechanisms and moderation procedures will be defined separately in the RAISE Hub operational model.</p>
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	<p>Direct engagement through consortium infrastructure partners; ESFRI and ERIC Forum channels; EOSC Association and EOSC-related channels; EuroHPC JU and AI Factory networks; EGI, GÉANT and OpenAIRE channels; national RI and national e-infrastructure networks; infrastructure conferences and policy events; AIS Summit sessions; RAISE Digital Hub; partner newsletters, targeted invitations and existing infrastructure community channels.</p>
KEY MESSAGES	<p>Help shape the infrastructure foundations for RAISE. Ensure AI-ready data, compute, services and access models reflect real community needs. Contribute to realistic and sustainable infrastructure upgrade scenarios. Support an interoperable, trustworthy and federated European AI in Science ecosystem.</p>
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	<p>Inputs to WP1 infrastructure mapping and good-practice registry; contributions to D2.1 and D2.2 where infrastructure enables scientific or AI for Science priorities; input to D3.1 on infrastructure, data, compute, access, governance and skills gaps; co-design input for D3.2 infrastructure upgrade scenarios; input to D3.3 cooperation mechanisms; feedback for D4.1 feasibility assessment and D4.2 roadmap; validation input for D5.1 SRIA.</p>
TIMELINE	<p>M1–M10: Identification and mobilisation of research infrastructure, e-infrastructure and scientific facility actors; contribution to WP1 infrastructure and initiative mapping, the AI in Science evidence base, and good-practice input.</p> <p>M8–M20: Active involvement in WP3 infrastructure gap analysis, infrastructure upgrade scenario co-design and cooperation mechanism discussions; contribution to relevant WP2 consultations where scientific or AI for Science priorities depend on data, compute, platforms, access, interoperability or services; feedback through the RAISE Digital Hub and AIS Summit-linked activities.</p> <p>M19–M30: Participation in WP4 feasibility assessment and roadmap consultation, and WP5 SRIA validation where infrastructure requirements, cooperation mechanisms and implementation feasibility are concerned; contribution to uptake and continuity discussions supported by the RAISE Digital Hub and RAISE Secretariat, with formal long-term governance and partnership mechanisms defined separately.</p>
RISKS & MITIGATION	<p>Risk: infrastructure heterogeneity, competing priorities, limited bandwidth, uneven AI readiness, overlap with existing EOSC/ESFRI/EuroHPC JU processes, and difficulty translating diverse needs into common scenarios. Mitigation: engage through existing infrastructure channels; use short and targeted consultations; align with existing roadmaps and governance structures; focus on concrete requirements and transferable good practices; use consortium partners for warm introductions; ensure Digital Hub summaries show how input is used.</p>

3.1.6 Policy Makers & Funding Organisations

Policy makers & funding organizations	
WHO	European and national policy actors and funders relevant to AI in Science and RAISE initiative, including the European Commission, Member States, national ministries of research/science/digital policy, national research councils and funding agencies, Programme Committee members, AI policy units, regulatory and advisory bodies, ERA Policy Agenda actors, and science executives involved in strategic research and infrastructure decision-making. This may also include national AI in Science initiatives and governance bodies where they provide policy-research coordination models.
WHY ENGAGE	Policy makers and funding organisations are essential for ensuring that the SRIA and roadmap are strategically relevant, aligned with EU and national priorities, and usable for future research, innovation and infrastructure investment decisions. Their involvement supports policy uptake, funding alignment, regulatory coherence, and the long-term sustainability of RAISE as a coordination structure for AI in Science.
WHAT WE NEED	Feedback on policy priorities for AI in Science; input on alignment with EU and national strategies, Horizon Europe, future framework programmes, ERA priorities, ESFRI, EOSC, EuroHPC JU, AI Factories, data spaces and relevant regulatory frameworks; guidance on AI Act, Data Act, ethics, IP, data protection and governance implications for research; feedback on SRIA recommendations, infrastructure roadmap feasibility, adoption pathways, and sustainability models; participation in strategic validation and capacity-building activities.
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	Primary: Governance & Legal; Innovation & Impact; strategic policy uptake. Secondary: Infrastructure & Platforms; Skills & Culture; Data & Open Science, especially where public investment, regulation, capacity building and national implementation are concerned.
KEY QUESTIONS	<p>How should AI in Science priorities align with EU and national policy agendas? What regulatory, governance and ethical issues must the SRIA address? How can the SRIA and roadmap inform future funding, infrastructure investment and national strategies? What policy levers can support AI adoption in research institutions and infrastructures? How can RAISE remain useful as a long-term European coordination mechanism?</p> <p>Where would European cooperation provide the greatest added value in advancing AI in Science priorities? Which SRIA priorities would benefit most from coordinated action across Member States, funding bodies, infrastructures and research communities? How could European, national and regional resources be better pooled to support shared priorities, for example, through joint funding, shared infrastructure access, coordinated skills programmes, common standards or cross-border cooperation mechanisms? How can the SRIA and roadmap help identify where fragmented efforts should be connected, scaled or aligned through RAISE as a long-term European coordination mechanism?</p>
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	CONSULT → INVOLVE. Policy actors are engaged through structured consultation, strategic validation and capacity-building activities. Their role is strongest in WP5 strategic alignment and SRIA validation, WP4 roadmap feasibility and uptake, and RAISE sustainability discussions. They may also contribute to WP3 cooperation mechanisms where governance and coordination models are discussed.
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	WP3 cooperation mechanism consultations where policy governance and coordination are relevant; WP4 feasibility and roadmap validation; WP5 strategic alignment mapping and targeted validation; bilateral discussions with European and national policymakers; public online consultation through the RAISE Digital Hub where appropriate; AIS Summit high-level sessions and policy roundtables; RAISE Academy 3-day bootcamp for ministries, funders, digital officers and science executives; policy briefings and targeted dissemination activities.
RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	Access SRIA, roadmap, evidence base, policy summaries and consultation materials; respond to public or targeted consultations where appropriate; follow summaries of how stakeholder feedback informs SRIA and roadmap development; access RAISE Academy outputs and reusable materials. Additional links: Policy actors will remain connected through the RAISE Digital Hub as a transparency, consultation, and uptake layer for SRIA, roadmap, policy summaries, and Academy outputs. The Hub will support continued access to evidence-based recommendations and future consultation cycles. Detailed governance roles, restricted access arrangements, formal partnership mechanisms, and moderation procedures will be defined separately in the RAISE Hub operational model.

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	European Commission and EU policy channels; national ministry and research council networks; Programme Committee and ERA-related channels; ESF and partner networks; AI Office / AI policy consultation spaces where relevant; EOSC, EuroHPC JU, ESFRI and AI Factory strategic forums; AIS Summit sessions; RAISE Digital Hub; policy briefings; targeted emails and bilateral meetings.
KEY MESSAGES	Use the SRIA and roadmap as evidence-based tools for coordinated AI in Science investment. Align AI in Science priorities with European and national strategies. Support trustworthy, responsible and competitive AI-enabled research. Help translate scientific and infrastructure needs into actionable policy and funding priorities.
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	Input to D3.3 where governance and cooperation mechanisms are addressed; feedback for D4.1 feasibility assessment and D4.2 implementation roadmap; strategic alignment input for WP5, including mapping against EU policy and regulatory frameworks; validation and uptake input for D5.1 SRIA; participation in RAISE Academy and policy briefings; input to sustainability and exploitation planning where relevant.
TIMELINE	M1–M10: policy landscape identification, early strategic alignment, initial EC/member state awareness, and links to relevant national or European policy initiatives. M8–M20: targeted input to cooperation mechanisms, infrastructure scenarios and emerging priorities; participation in AIS Summit feedback and policy discussions. M19–M30: SRIA and roadmap validation, policy uptake discussions, RAISE Academy participation, and contribution to sustainability and continuity planning.
RISKS & MITIGATION	Risk: competing policy agendas, regulatory uncertainty, limited availability of senior policy actors, political changes, and difficulty translating technical recommendations into policy action. Mitigation: use concise evidence-based policy messages; align with existing EU and national frameworks; combine public consultation with targeted bilateral engagement; involve policy actors at key validation moments; use the RAISE Academy to support informed decision-making; keep recommendations adaptable to evolving regulatory and funding contexts.

3.1.7 Civil Society and Societal Stakeholders

Civil Society and Societal Stakeholders	
WHO	Citizen science networks, public stakeholders, NGOs, public engagement organisations, science museums, patient and environmental organisations, AI ethics and digital rights groups, community-based research groups, and relevant citizen-science initiatives. This includes European and national citizen-science communities such as ECSA-linked networks and domain-specific citizen-science projects where relevant.
WHY ENGAGE	Civil society engagement supports the legitimacy, transparency and responsible uptake of AI in Science. These actors help ensure that SRIA recommendations reflect societal concerns, public trust, ethical expectations, accessibility needs, and the broader societal value of AI-enabled research. Their involvement strengthens responsible research and innovation and helps avoid a purely technical or expert-only perspective.
WHAT WE NEED	Input on societal priorities and concerns related to AI in research; perspectives on trust, transparency, explainability, fairness, accessibility and public accountability; citizen-science use cases involving AI; examples of public engagement and responsible AI practices; feedback on societal impact claims; views on how AI-enabled science can serve public benefit while respecting ethical and legal expectations.
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	Primary: Trust & Integrity; Governance & Legal; Innovation & Impact. Secondary: Skills & Culture, especially public AI literacy and awareness; Data & Open Science, especially where citizen science, open data and public access are relevant; Scientific Priorities where societal challenges are directly involved.
KEY QUESTIONS	What makes AI-enabled science trustworthy from a public perspective? What types of transparency and explanation are needed? What ethical safeguards should guide AI in Science? Which societal benefits should AI-enabled research prioritise? How can citizen-science and public-engagement practices contribute to responsible AI in Science? How can outputs be communicated in accessible and inclusive ways?

ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	CONSULT → INVOLVE. Civil society actors are mainly engaged through public consultation, targeted feedback, citizen-science links, and responsible AI discussions. Their role is strongest in validating trust, ethics, accessibility, societal impact and public-interest aspects of the SRIA, rather than in technical drafting. Selective involvement in workshops may be considered where citizen-science or societal-impact expertise is directly relevant.
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	WP1 good-practice identification where citizen-science or public-engagement cases are relevant; targeted input to responsible AI, trust and societal-impact discussions; selected participation in WP2 or WP3 activities where societal challenges, ethics, access or citizen-science data are directly relevant; RAISE Digital Hub public consultations, surveys and feedback mechanisms; AIS Summit public engagement sessions where appropriate; WP5 public online consultation on SRIA and roadmap.
RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	Access public-facing summaries, SRIA and roadmap consultation materials, good-practice resources and accessible explanations of project outputs; respond to public consultations; contribute examples of citizen-science or responsible AI practices; provide feedback on trust, transparency, accessibility and societal relevance. The Hub should support civil society participation through clear language, accessible formats, moderated consultation spaces and visible summaries of how feedback is used. Civil society actors will remain connected through the public-facing layer of the RAISE Digital Hub. The Hub will support continued access to accessible outputs, public consultation opportunities, good-practice resources and summaries of SRIA/roadmap developments.
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	RAISE Digital Hub, partner newsletters, social media campaigns, public events, science festivals, citizen-science networks such as ECSA-linked channels, science museums, public engagement organisations, patient or environmental networks where relevant, and accessible summaries distributed through partner and community channels.
KEY MESSAGES	Help ensure AI in Science serves society. Your perspective strengthens trustworthy, transparent and responsible AI-enabled research. Contribute to public-interest priorities, ethical safeguards and accessible communication around AI in Science.
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	Input to WP1 good-practice registry where citizen-science or public-engagement examples are relevant; feedback on trust, transparency, accessibility and societal-impact aspects of the SRIA; input to WP5 public consultation; recommendations on responsible AI communication and public trust; validation of societal benefit and ethical considerations where relevant.
TIMELINE	M1–M10: identification of relevant citizen-science, public engagement and civil society networks; contribution to WP1 good-practice and responsible AI input where relevant. M8–M20: targeted consultation on trust, ethics, accessibility and societal impact; participation in selected Digital Hub consultations and AIS Summit engagement activities where appropriate. M19–M30: public consultation on SRIA and roadmap; validation of societal relevance and accessible communication; preparation of continued public engagement through the RAISE Hub.
RISKS & MITIGATION	Risk: low engagement, AI anxiety, lack of accessible language, consultation fatigue, difficulty reaching diverse publics, or limited relevance of technical SRIA topics for wider audiences. Mitigation: use clear and accessible language; work through trusted citizen-science and public engagement networks; focus consultation questions on trust, ethics, public benefit and accessibility; provide short consultation formats; clearly show how feedback is used; avoid over-technical framing.

3.1.8 Industry & Innovation Actors

Industry & innovation actors	
WHO	Industry and innovation actors relevant to AI in Science, including AI/ML companies, SMEs, startups, research technology providers, data service providers, HPC/cloud and platform providers, publishers and scholarly communication service providers, pharma/biotech and manufacturing R&D actors, GenAI and foundation model companies, industry R&D labs, and industry associations or public-private networks such as BDVA and ADRA.
WHY ENGAGE	Industry and innovation actors help connect scientific priorities with emerging technologies, market capabilities, standards, interoperability needs, and innovation pathways. Their involvement supports the Innovation & Impact dimension of the SRIA, helps identify barriers and enablers for uptake, and provides insight into sustainable service models, public-private cooperation, and technology trends relevant to AI-enabled science.
WHAT WE NEED	<p>Industry perspectives on AI in Science uptake, technology trends, market readiness, service models, standards and interoperability; input on AI/data/compute platforms, research technology tools, cloud/HPC services, and foundation model capabilities; examples of responsible innovation and AI-enabled research services; views on IP, data-sharing, skills and talent pipelines; feedback on infrastructure upgrade scenarios, roadmap feasibility, and innovation-oriented SRIA recommendations.</p> <p>Industry perspectives on AI in Science uptake, technology trends, market readiness, service models, standards and interoperability; input on AI/data/compute platforms, research technology tools, cloud/HPC services, AI Factories, and foundation model capabilities; overview of the AI in Science start-up landscape, including maturity, commercial potential and domain-specific opportunities for AI for Science tools and services; needs of current and potential AI in Science start-up founders, including access to compute, data, infrastructure, funding, mentoring, regulatory guidance, test environments, customers and research partnerships; examples of responsible innovation and AI-enabled research services; views on IP, data-sharing, skills and talent pipelines; feedback on infrastructure upgrade scenarios, roadmap feasibility, innovation-oriented SRIA recommendations, and ways industry can support, partner with or benefit from AI in Science start-ups.</p>
SRIA FOCUS AREAS	<p>Primary: Innovation & Impact; Infrastructure & Platforms.</p> <p>Secondary: Skills & Culture; Data & Open Science; Governance & Legal, especially where standards, IP, data-sharing, compliance and responsible innovation are concerned.</p>
KEY QUESTIONS	How can AI in Science priorities translate into innovation and real-world impact? What technology trends should the SRIA and roadmap anticipate? What standards, interoperability mechanisms, service models or data-sharing arrangements are needed? What barriers limit academia-industry collaboration and technology uptake? What skills and talent gaps affect AI-enabled science? How can open science principles be balanced with responsible innovation and IP considerations?
ENGAGEMENT LEVEL	CONSULT → INVOLVE. Industry actors are engaged through structured consultation, targeted expert input, innovation and infrastructure discussions, and validation of SRIA and roadmap recommendations. Their role is strongest where technology capabilities, infrastructure services, standards, uptake, skills, and innovation pathways are addressed.
ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES	WP1 landscape mapping and good-practice identification where industry use cases or service models are relevant; WP2 transversal AI for Science workshops where industry expertise supports AI methods, tools, frugal AI, data processing or workflow innovation; WP2 interdisciplinary cooperation discussions where academia-industry collaboration is relevant; WP3 infrastructure gap and scenario consultations; WP4 feasibility and roadmap feedback; WP5 SRIA and strategic alignment consultations; AIS Summit industry, matchmaking or innovation sessions where relevant; RAISE Digital Hub consultations, thematic forums, surveys and feedback mechanisms.

RAISE DIGITAL HUB ROLE	<p>Access SRIA, roadmap, infrastructure and innovation-related outputs; respond to targeted consultations; contribute use cases, good practices and feedback on technology trends, standards, interoperability, services and uptake barriers; participate in thematic discussions where relevant; follow summaries of how industry input informs SRIA and roadmap development. The Hub supports structured engagement through surveys, feedback collection, thematic forums and consultation spaces. The Hub will support continued access to SRIA and roadmap outputs, good-practice resources, technology and standards discussions, and future consultation opportunities. Detailed governance roles, access rights, partnership mechanisms, conflict-of-interest handling and moderation procedures will be defined separately in the RAISE Hub operational model.</p>
COMMUNICATION CHANNELS	<p>BDVA and ADRA channels, industry associations, innovation networks, partner networks, direct outreach, LinkedIn and targeted campaigns, industry and AI/data events, EBDVF, AI Factories and data-space-related forums, AIS Summit sessions, RAISE Digital Hub, newsletters, and sector-specific events where relevant.</p>
KEY MESSAGES	<p>Shape the AI in Science innovation ecosystem. Help connect scientific excellence with responsible technology uptake. Contribute to sustainable, interoperable and trustworthy AI-enabled research services. Bring industry insight into infrastructure, standards, skills and impact pathways.</p>
EXPECTED OUTPUTS	<p>Inputs to WP1 mapping and good-practice registry where industry use cases are relevant; input to D2.2 on AI for Science R&I priorities; input to D2.3 on interdisciplinary and cross-sector cooperation; input to D3.1 on technology, service, data and compute gaps; co-design input for D3.2 infrastructure upgrade scenarios; input to D3.3 cooperation mechanisms where public-private coordination is relevant; feedback for D4.1 feasibility assessment and D4.2 roadmap; innovation and uptake feedback for D5.1 SRIA.</p>
TIMELINE	<p>M1–M10: identify and mobilise relevant industry and innovation actors; map industry-linked AI services, technologies, networks and good-practice examples. M8–M20: targeted involvement in WP2 transversal/interdisciplinary workshops, WP3 infrastructure and cooperation consultations, AIS Summit activities and Digital Hub consultations. M19–M30: feedback on feasibility, roadmap and SRIA validation; contribution to uptake, sustainability and continuity discussions through the RAISE Hub and Secretariat.</p>
RISKS & MITIGATION	<p>Risk: conflicting interests, IP concerns, commercial bias, uneven participation from SMEs and large companies, or tension between open science and commercial models. Mitigation: use transparent engagement principles; clarify boundaries between consultation and endorsement; balance industry input with academic, infrastructure and policy perspectives; address IP and data-sharing issues explicitly; focus on shared value, interoperability, responsible innovation and open science compatibility.</p>

SCIENCE Stakeholder Ecosystem and Engagement Logic

3.2 Stakeholder Engagement Lifecycle (M1–M30)

Stakeholder Engagement Lifecycle (M1-M30)			
Work package & key tasks	Timeframe & phase	Stakeholders engaged	Key engagement activities & outputs
WP1 – AI in Science Landscape Analysis – T1.1 <i>State of the art for scientific research using AI</i> ; T1.2 <i>State of the art for AI research & innovations</i> ; T1.3 <i>Landscape analysis of AI infrastructures & initiatives</i> ; T1.4 <i>Good-practice registry</i>	M1–M10 (Phase 1) – Knowledge consolidation	Research communities; AI experts & researchers; research infrastructures; industry & innovation actors.	Meta-analysis of roadmaps, white papers and literature; mapping AI infrastructures; identification of emerging technologies; collection of good practices (ethics, openness, frugality) with >40 documented cases; dashboard and registry on the RAISE Digital Hub; contributes evidence base for WP2/3.
WP2 – Research & AI priorities – T2.1 <i>Scientific challenge priorities</i> ; T2.2 <i>AI for Science research & innovation priorities</i> ; T2.3 <i>Interdisciplinary cooperation priorities</i>	M8–M20 (Phase 2) – Co-creation of priorities.	AISWG experts (domain scientists, AI researchers, citizen scientists); research communities; infrastructures; civil society; industry; policy makers	Five domain-specific workshops (one per pilot area); five transversal AI-for-Science workshops (topics: open science, data processing, experimental design, automation, frugal AI); interdisciplinary workshop on cooperation priorities; workshops collocated with major scientific or AI conferences; Digital Hub consultations and AIS Summit sessions; mid-term SAB feedback.

<p>WP3 – Infrastructure & cooperation mechanisms – T3.1 <i>Gap analysis</i>; T3.2 <i>Infrastructure upgrade scenarios</i>; T3.3 <i>Cooperation mechanisms</i></p>	<p>M8–M20 (Phase 2) – Infrastructure design & cooperation.</p>	<p>Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures & scientific facilities; research communities; AI experts; industry & innovation actors; policy makers.</p>	<p>Expert workshop to analyse gaps in hardware, software, data workflows, skills and governance; participatory design sessions to draft 3–5 upgrade scenarios covering compute, data spaces and services; targeted consultations (15–20 expert interviews and focus groups) to design cooperation mechanisms for RAISE; feedback via Digital Hub and AIS Summit.</p>
<p>WP4 – Feasibility & Roadmap – T4.1 <i>Feasibility assessment</i>; T4.2 <i>AI in Science implementation roadmap</i></p>	<p>M19–M30 (Phase 3) – Consolidation & implementation.</p>	<p>Infrastructure providers & user communities; AISWG experts; research communities; policy makers & funders; industry & civil society.</p>	<p>Multi-criteria analysis of priority scenarios and cooperation models via expert workshops to assess impact, readiness and cost; joint feasibility report (D4.1); development of a phased implementation roadmap (D4.2) with short-, medium- and long-term actions; joint public consultation with SRIA; validation through Digital Hub, AIS Summit and final SAB review.</p>
<p>WP5 – AI in Science SRIA – T5.1 <i>Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda</i>; T5.2 <i>Community feedback & alignment with EU initiatives</i></p>	<p>M21–M30 (Phase 3) – SRIA development & alignment.</p>	<p>All stakeholder groups; SAB; policy makers & funding organisations; civil society.</p>	<p>Integrate outputs from WP1–WP4 into the SRIA (D5.1), focusing on trustworthy & frugal AI; map SRIA & roadmap recommendations against EU policies (AI Act, Data Act, Digital Europe, etc.); coordinated online consultation and targeted validation sessions; final integration and endorsement through Digital Hub, AIS Summits, RAISE Academy and SAB strategic review.</p>
<p>WP6 – Coordination & governance (Phase 1–2) – T6.1 <i>Project coordination & management</i>; T6.2 <i>SAB set-up & liaison</i>; T6.3 <i>AI in Science Working Groups</i>; T6.4 <i>Ethics, inclusion & DMP</i></p>	<p>M1–M20 – Establish coordination & advisory interfaces</p>	<p>SCIANCE Management Committee (MC); SAB; AISWG; consortium partners</p>	<p>Produce Project Handbook (D6.1); launch call for expression of interest and select AISWG experts; prepare Terms of Reference (D6.2 & D6.3); appoint SAB by M6, organise orientation and mid-term meeting; onboard experts and align with WP1 evidence; develop and update the Data Management Plan; support ethical and inclusive engagement.</p>
<p>WP7 – Coordination & governance (Phase 3) – T7.1 <i>Project coordination & management</i>; T7.2 <i>SAB liaison</i>; T7.3 <i>AISWG operations</i>; T7.4 <i>Ethics, inclusion & DMP</i></p>	<p>M21–M30 – Final coordination & review</p>	<p>Management committee (MC); SAB; AISWG; consortium partners</p>	<p>Update Project Handbook; coordinate final reporting and deliverables; convene final SAB meeting for strategic review; organise final AISWG review and consensus building; maintain DMP; ensure compliance and wrap-up activities.</p>
<p>WP8 – Communication & stakeholder engagement (Phase 1–2) – T8.1 <i>Communication, dissemination & Digital Hub</i>; T8.2 <i>Stakeholder mapping & engagement strategy</i>; T8.3 <i>AIS Summits & consultation tools</i>; T8.4 <i>RAISE Secretariat & sustainability pilot</i></p>	<p>M1–M20 – Launch engagement infrastructure</p>	<p>All stakeholder communities; AISWG; SAB</p>	<p>Develop communication strategy and visual identity; create & maintain the RAISE Digital Hub as the central portal for resources, consultations and updates; map and prioritise stakeholders and define engagement channels; organise AIS Summit 2025 and associated workshops/roundtables; provide digital consultation tools; establish and pilot the RAISE Secretariat to coordinate engagement and sustainability.</p>

WP9 – Communication, engagement & capacity building (Phase 3) – T9.1 <i>Communication & Digital Hub</i> ; T9.2 <i>Stakeholder mapping & engagement</i> ; T9.3 <i>AIS Summits & consultation tools</i> ; T9.4 <i>RAISE Secretariat & sustainability</i> ; T9.5 <i>RAISE Academy bootcamp</i>	M21–M30 – Final engagement & sustainability	All stakeholder communities; high-level policy leads & funders (RAISE Academy)	Continue communication and Digital Hub activities to promote SRIA and roadmap uptake; refresh stakeholder mapping and engagement strategy; organise the final AIS Summit (2026) with sessions for validation and matchmaking; operate the RAISE Secretariat to pilot long-term functions; design and deliver the RAISE Academy bootcamp for strategic leadership at the third AIS Summit, targeting ministries, funding bodies and R&I executives.
---	---	--	--

4 Communication Strategy

4.1 Communication Approach

The SCIANCE communication strategy focuses on building a recognisable project identity and building a base audience for ‘AI in Science’ in general and RAISE Digital Hub in particular.

We will deploy tailored messaging across diverse channels to ensure project objectives resonate with all stakeholders.

4.2 Branding and Visual Identity for SCIANCE and RAISE

A SCIANCE branding framework¹ has been established at an early stage of the project to ensure a consistent and recognisable visual identity across all communication, dissemination, and engagement activities. It provides the strategic foundation for how SCIANCE presents itself across internal and external channels, ensuring coherence across the RAISE Digital Hub, events programme, training activities, and external outreach.

In parallel, SCIANCE contributes to the coordination of the emerging RAISE and AI science ecosystem visual identity in its role as interim ecosystem alignment mechanism.

4.2.1 RAISE Branding Framework

The RAISE branding framework is established at European Commission level and applies across all contributing projects. SCIANCE operationalises this framework in its role as the interim coordination and alignment mechanism for the emerging AI in Science ecosystem, ensuring consistent, coherent, and EC-compliant communication across all RAISE-related activities (see current draft of the RAISE Branding & Co-Branding Guidelines).

The purpose of the framework is to ensure ecosystem-wide coherence in communication and dissemination, while preserving the autonomy of individual projects and enabling structured visibility of contributions to RAISE. It provides a common reference system that supports trust-building, recognisability, and alignment across distributed initiatives, without creating a standalone RAISE brand.

Within this context, SCIANCE plays a key operational and governance role in implementing and overseeing the application of branding principles. Building on EC requirements and SCIANCE-developed communication resources, SCIANCE acts as the primary coordination and approval layer for the use of shared ecosystem visual elements in RAISE-related contexts. This ensures that branding is applied consistently, appropriately, and in line with agreed guidelines.

The RAISE Branding & Co-Branding Guidelines are being developed. The current draft can be found here². The final version will be available through the RAISE Digital Hub Resources.

4.3 Communication & dissemination toolkit

The Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Toolkit operationalises the SCIANCE communication and branding framework by providing a structured set of reusable materials that support consistent implementation across all dissemination and engagement activities.

It ensures coherent application of SCIANCE communication principles across the RAISE Digital Hub, events programme, training activities, and external outreach, enabling partners to translate strategic communication objectives into practice.

¹ <https://cdn.sciance.eu/app/uploads/2026/02/SCIANCE-Brandguide.pdf>

² [RAISE Branding & Co-Branding Guidelines](#)

The Toolkit includes templates, campaign materials, social media assets, and implementation guidance to support aligned messaging, dissemination activities, and stakeholder engagement across the consortium.

It is a living resource, updated throughout the project to reflect evolving communication needs and stakeholder feedback, ensuring consistency, efficiency, and amplification of SCIANCE communication outputs.

4.4 Communication Channels and Tools

Channel	Stakeholders	Goal	Status M6
Communication Packages and Branding Toolkit	Project Partners	Ensure consistent and timely communication to all stakeholders via partner networks, via ready-made templates, visuals and messages	Brand guide delivered (M1) Communications packages for launch and AISWG call delivered, packages planned for all future campaigns Document and presentation templates available
SCIANCE project Website	All	Information about project, news, activities, calls and events. Information Hub in the first phase of the project (to be replaced by the Digital Hub) News items and press releases	Temporary project website launched by M2 at https://www.sciance.eu M4: 5562 unique visitors
SCIANCE LinkedIn	All	Information about project, news, activities, calls and events. Campaigns to reach specific stakeholders such as policy makers or industry Promote specific campaigns	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sciance4raise (M1) M4: 338 subscribers
SCIANCE Newsletter	All	Information about project, news, activities, calls and events. Promote specific campaigns	Active M1 M4: 87 subscribers
RAISE Digital Hub	All:	RAISE Digital Hub Content Layer: Public-facing content hub with SCIANCE, RAISE and broader AI science ecosystem news, events, resources, dashboards, good practices digest of training resources, and access to RAISE Forum	Concept and architecture defined (two-layer model: content + engagement) CMS requirements and platform design validated with European Commission (May) Sitemap, UX structure, and minimal content architecture finalised Development with provider initiated (WordPress)
	All, especially AIS Working Groups, AI & Science Community, and invited experts	RAISE Forum Engagement Layer: Enable two-way communication and structured interaction with stakeholders through discussions, consultations, and feedback mechanisms. Support targeted communication of draft outputs, consultation	Platform setup and configuration ongoing User access model and governance framework defined (Working Groups, AI & Science Community, Public layer) Initial deployment planned for M5–M6 (internal pilot phase).

		materials, and working group activities to engaged stakeholders. Facilitate collection of stakeholder input (polls, surveys, discussions) to inform SRIA and roadmap development.	
Partner networks	Project Partners	Information about project, news, activities, calls and events. Cross-posting strategy across partner institutional channels thanks to information packages	All partners are forwarding information via their own networks
Document Repository	All	Ensure structured and long-term access to SCIANCE outputs and project-related documents. Provide a user-friendly entry point to resources via the RAISE Digital Hub, while ensuring persistent storage, citation, and compliance through external repositories.	Approach defined: – RAISE Digital Hub “Resource Hub” to provide curated access to publications and outputs (one entry per resource) – Zenodo used for storage and publication of deliverables and strategic outputs (DOI assignment, metadata, long-term preservation).
Publications (whitepapers, guides, and factsheets)	All	Information about specific campaigns. Digestible, language based, versions of main project outputs.	First materials (card with QR code) in production
Printables	All	Cards with QR references; Posters; Flyers; Roll ups allowing communication about SCIANCE activities & results (including SRIA) at a glance	Designs in preparation First prints in preparation
Audiovisual content	All	Infographs, clips, animations allowing visual and image-based communication about SCIANCE activities & results (including SRIA) at a glance	In preparation

4.5 RAISE Digital Hub

The RAISE Digital Hub is the central digital entry point for SCIANCE and RAISE communication, dissemination, and ecosystem engagement. It combines editorial publication and community interaction in a single integrated environment, ensuring both high-quality curated content and active stakeholder participation.

The Hub consists of:

- RAISE Digital Hub (WordPress – science4raise.eu)**
A curated, editorially governed platform providing structured access to SCIENCE outputs, including project results, SRIA-related materials, good practices, events, and strategic communication content. This layer ensures consistency, quality control, and long-term accessibility of validated outputs. Content may also include selected external resources (e.g. papers or calls) when they are reviewed and approved by the SCIENCE team.
- RAISE Forum (Discourse – forum.science4raise.eu)**
As an integrated part of the Digital Hub that enables consultations, discussions, and collaborative knowledge exchange. This layer facilitates stakeholders to actively contribute to SRIA development, validate outputs, and participate in thematic exchanges across AI in Science domains. In addition, the Forum may host structured community-generated resources (e.g. reading lists, thematic compilations, and reference collections), which can be curated and referenced within the Digital Hub.
- RAISE Observatory (OpenAIREgraph – observatory.science4raise.eu)**
The RAISE Observatory is the analytics and discovery layer of the Digital Hub, providing a structured view of the European AI in Science ecosystem. It enables users to explore and analyse key actors, organisations, infrastructures, projects, funding programmes, and publications, supporting ecosystem mapping and strategic insight.
- The Observatory integrates a Landscape Analysis tool within the “Explore” section of the Hub, combining OpenAIREgraph data with a consistent RAISE user experience. It provides visualisations and selected embedded functionalities via iframe, while more advanced analytical features are accessible through external OpenAIRE-hosted dashboards. The interface is aligned with the RAISE visual identity and implemented following the EGI’s Figma design system for the RAISE Digital Hub.

The separation of layers ensures a clear functional distinction: formal publication and dissemination activities are handled through the content layer, while interaction, feedback, and co-creation are enabled through the community layer.

The community layer is structured around AI in Science Working Groups (five domain-specific and five cross-cutting), enabling persistent and traceable engagement beyond individual events or workshops. It supports asynchronous expert deliberation, consultation processes, and collaborative development of research and innovation priorities.

Key engagement functionalities include structured discussion categories, polls and voting mechanisms, topic templates, tagging systems, and mailing-list mode interaction. These features enable both lightweight participation and in-depth expert exchange, depending on stakeholder needs.

The Digital Hub directly supports SCIANCE objectives by functioning as the primary digital entry point for the project and the wider AI in Science ecosystem. It replaces a traditional project website (the lightweight website launched at the project start will be discontinued once the Digital Hub is launched) and consolidates all communication, dissemination, and engagement functions into a single integrated environment, while applying the RAISE branding framework in line with EC communication requirements.

In this role, the Hub enables:

- structured stakeholder consultation for SRIA co-creation and validation
- continuous engagement across AIS Working Groups and thematic communities
- dissemination of SCIANCE project outputs, good practices, and strategic materials
- publication and visibility of project news, events, and ecosystem activities
- collection and synthesis of stakeholder feedback across WP1–WP5 activities
- long-term accessibility, discoverability, and reusability of knowledge resources

The Hub therefore acts as both the SCIANCE communication platform and the primary access point to RAISE-aligned ecosystem activities, ensuring that project-level and ecosystem-level information is presented in a coherent, structured, and user-oriented manner.

4.6 Targeted Communication Campaigns

SCIANCE implements phased, audience-targeted communication campaigns aligned with the project lifecycle, ensuring continuity from awareness raising to uptake and policy impact. Early campaigns (M1–M4) established strong visibility and validated outreach mechanisms, exceeding initial engagement targets.

Campaign	Timeline	Objective	Target Audiences	Key Activities	Channels & Tools	Key KPIs / Results	Key Message
Project Release Campaign	M1–M4	Establish project visibility and launch communication channels	All stakeholders	Launch of website, newsletter, social media; partner outreach	Website, LinkedIn, newsletter, partner networks	Channels operational by M1 (ahead of M3); 550 newsletter subscribers ; 4,225 website visits	SCIANCE establishes its communication presence and stakeholder entry points
AISWG Call Campaign	M2–M4	Mobilise stakeholder participation in AI in Science Working Groups	Scientists, policymakers, industry, research support staff	Targeted outreach, campaign materials, survey dissemination	Website, LinkedIn, partner networks, mailing lists	Target: 500 → Achieved: 650+ registrations	Join and contribute to the AI in Science Working Groups shaping European priorities
RAISE Digital Hub Launch	M6–M10	Drive adoption of the Digital Hub as the central engagement platform	Scientific community, AI experts, infrastructure, policymakers	Platform launch, onboarding, feature promotion, stakeholder activation	Digital Hub, events, newsletters, partner channels	Platform traffic, user registrations, engagement rates	The RAISE Digital Hub is the central gateway for AI in Science in Europe
AI for Science,	M6–M20	Strengthen visibility and cross-	Scientists, industry, policymakers,	Storytelling campaigns, workshops,	Digital Hub, newsletter	Engagement rates, participation	AI enables scientific discovery

Europe-Wide		domain collaboration on AI in Science	infrastructure, networks	AIS Summit promotion, stakeholder highlights	s, social media, events	n in events, stakeholder contributions	across disciplines through shared European collaboration
Co-Creating the SRIA	M10–M26	Support structured consultation and validation of the SRIA	Scientific community, AI experts, policymakers, infrastructure, industry	Consultations, workshops, working group discussions	Digital Hub forum, AIS Summits, targeted outreach	Participation levels, diversity of input, feedback quality	Stakeholders co-create the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for AI in Science
SRIA Launch & Adoption	M24–M30	Maximise visibility, uptake, and policy integration of final outputs	Policymakers, funders, infrastructure	Final dissemination event, policy briefs, media outreach	AIS Summit, policy channels, Digital Hub, partner networks	Event participation (>80), downloads, citations, policy uptake	The SRIA provides the reference framework for AI in Science in Europe

5 Dissemination Strategy

5.1 Dissemination Approach

The SCIANCE Dissemination Strategy is focused on long-term adoption, integration, and impact of project outputs. This dissemination strategy is underpinned by the communication measures described above – based on early and broad visibility, multi-channel engagement, audience targeting, and adaptive monitoring of results.

The strategy is structured around three complementary pillars:

1 Visibility and Awareness

SCIANCE ensures broad visibility of AI in Science activities, methods, and results through coordinated dissemination across digital channels, partner networks, and stakeholder communities, increasing awareness of project outputs and ecosystem developments.

2 Community Building, Knowledge Sharing and Co-Creation

The project fosters active stakeholder engagement through co-creation processes, including the definition of research and innovation priorities, cross-domain collaboration, and academia–industry interaction. It supports the development of shared knowledge and strengthens synergies across networks and disciplines.

3 Uptake and Sustainability

Dissemination activities are designed to maximise the long-term use of project results by aligning outputs with strategic initiatives, supporting infrastructure and governance scenarios, and ensuring that key outcomes—including the SRIA—are adopted by relevant stakeholders and ecosystems.

5.2 Events programme

The SCIANCE events programme is a core mechanism for stakeholder engagement, co-creation, dissemination, and validation of project outputs. It provides structured opportunities for interaction between SCIANCE and different stakeholder groups, ensuring continuous feedback loops throughout the project lifecycle.

The events programme operationalises the SCIANCE engagement strategy by providing structured interaction points mapped onto the AISWG co-creation layer, the SCIANCE SAB strategic alignment layer, and the broader stakeholder consultation processes coordinated through WP8/9 and the RAISE Digital Hub. Each event type corresponds to a specific function in the SRIA lifecycle, including evidence building (WP1), co-creation (WP2–WP3), consultation and validation (WP4–WP5), and external ecosystem alignment.

The programme is designed as a multi-format and multi-level engagement framework, combining SCIANCE-led events with participation in high-impact external conferences and ecosystem events – online and in-person.

5.2.1 SCIANCE-led and Strategic events

In addition to SCIANCE-led activities, the events programme includes AIS Summit, a strategic event where SCIANCE plays a significant role in shaping content, facilitating discussions, and contributing to outcomes, while not acting as the primary organiser.

Activity	Aim	Stakeholders	Timing
AIS Summit Participation	Cross-layer synthesis, validation, and ecosystem alignment of SRIA outputs across AISWGs, SAB, and stakeholder communities	All stakeholders	M10, M22, M29
Information & Training Webinars	Present SCIANCE activities, collect stakeholder input, disseminate SCIANCE outcomes, training		
Thematic workshops	Domain-specific challenges and SRIA input	Researchers, infrastructures	M6–M15
Consultation sessions	Iterative SRIA development	Experts, policymakers	Ongoing
Final dissemination event	Presentation of SRIA and outputs	All stakeholders	M29

Events are structured according to their function within the SCIANCE engagement framework:

Co-creation events

Thematic workshops (WP2 / WP3)

- Feed into the development of draft SRIA priorities and AI in Science Roadmap inputs
- Engage AISWG experts, researchers, AI experts, and infrastructure providers

Validation events

AIS Summits

- Consolidate and validate SRIA and roadmap outputs across stakeholder groups
- Provide structured interaction between AISWGs and the broader ecosystem

Consultation events

Consultation sessions (Digital Hub-enabled)

- Collect wider community feedback on draft priorities and roadmap elements
- Engage policy actors, industry, civil society, and research communities

Dissemination events

Final dissemination event

- Present final SRIA, roadmap, and key SCIANCE outputs to the full ecosystem
- Support uptake and long-term visibility of results

5.2.2 External events participation and strategy

SCIANCE will actively engage in key European and international events (e.g. EOSC Symposium, EBDVF, IDW, AI Factories forums, GenAI4EU events, and others), ensuring visibility, alignment, and integration within relevant policy, research, and innovation ecosystems. Through this participation, SCIANCE positions itself as an active contributor to the broader AI in Science and European research landscape, while maximising the uptake and impact of its results beyond the consortium.

External events serve both dissemination and structured ecosystem validation purposes. They provide opportunities for co-creation and validation of the SRIA, dissemination of project outputs and results, strengthening of cross-domain collaboration, engagement of policy and infrastructure stakeholders, and building long-term ecosystem connections. In addition, they function as strategic feedback channels with European initiatives, enabling validation of infrastructure assumptions, policy coherence checks, and refinement of uptake pathways for SRIA outputs. Insights gathered through these activities are fed back into SCIANCE engagement processes via the RAISE Digital Hub and WP5 coordination activities.

SCIANCE engagement in external events also ensures alignment with key EU initiatives and frameworks (e.g. RAISE, EOSC, EuroHPC JU, ESFRI), supporting coherence with wider European research and infrastructure strategies, while fostering partnerships and collaboration opportunities across domains.

Participation follows a structured approach covering European policy and research events (including EOSC Symposium, EBDVF, IDW, AI Factories forums, and GenAI4EU events), thematic conferences and scientific workshops, AI and digital research infrastructure networks, and strategic stakeholder forums and advisory platforms. These activities are coordinated across WP8/9 and informed by AISWG outputs, SAB strategic guidance, and RAISE Digital Hub consultation insights to ensure consistency with the SCIANCE engagement architecture.

External participation is centrally coordinated through a shared SharePoint tracking system to ensure strategic targeting of high-impact events and audiences, avoid duplication, and maximise outreach efficiency. Event selection is guided by SRIA development needs, AISWG and SAB priorities, and identified gaps in infrastructure, policy, and innovation ecosystems.

5.3 Training and capacity building (RAISE Academy)

The RAISE Academy will be SCIANCE's dedicated training and capacity-building framework, designed to strengthen skills, knowledge, and institutional readiness for AI-enabled science across Europe.

It plays a critical role in ensuring that stakeholders, particularly policymakers, infrastructure providers, and research leaders, are equipped to understand, adopt, and implement AI in Science approaches aligned with the SRIA. The RAISE Academy will be organised towards the end of the project as part of Task 9.1, and its concrete formats are still to be defined and will be further shaped during implementation.

Objectives

The RAISE Academy aims to build capacity for AI adoption in scientific research, support decision-makers in strategic investment and policy design, promote understanding of AI in Science methodologies and infrastructures, ensure equitable access to knowledge across stakeholder groups, and support long-term sustainability of SCIANCE outputs.

Integration with SCIANCE activities

RAISE Academy activities are closely linked to SRIA development and validation processes, AIS Summits and thematic workshops, Digital Hub training resources and stakeholder consultations and engagement processes.

Expected outcomes include increased AI literacy among key stakeholder groups, improved readiness for infrastructure and policy implementation, stronger alignment between research priorities and funding strategies, and enhanced uptake of SRIA recommendations.

5.4 Domains

To ensure a coherent, sustainable, and future-proof digital presence for the SCIANCE project and the RAISE Digital Hub, a set of domain names has been secured and evaluated in line with European Commission guidance and implementation needs.

5.3.1 Domain Architecture

The project adopts a layered domain structure:

Domain	Purpose	Status
raise4science.eu	Main entry point	Active
science.eu	Project identity redirect once hub is launched	Active
AIS Summit domains	Event continuity	Registered

5.3.2 Domain Sustainability and Governance

All domains are currently managed by EGI Foundation as WP8/9 lead to enable operational continuity during the project implementation phase. In line with the long-term sustainability strategy, domain ownership will be transferred to ESF or a future RAISE governance entity to ensure continuity beyond the project lifetime.

5.4 Summary of Key Dissemination Activities

Activity	Alm	Stakeholders	Status M5
AISWG: establishment and activation	Community-Building Activities Co-Create Research Challenge Priorities Co-Develop AI Research and Innovation Priorities Foster Cross-Domain Collaboration Establish Cross-Network Synergies Foster Academia-Industry Collaborations	All	650+ expressions Evaluation ongoing
SCIANCE Website/ RAISE Digital Hub	Promote AI in Science Methods Extend Awareness Amplify Outputs Broaden Reach	All	Project Website live Digital Hub in preparation
RAISE Academy	Community-Building Activities Co-Create Research Challenge Priorities Co-Develop AI Research and Innovation Priorities Foster Cross-Domain Collaboration Establish Cross-Network Synergies Foster Academia-Industry Collaborations	Research Communities AI Experts and Technology Developers Research Infrastructures (incl. ESFRI, EOSC, e-Infrastructures, HPC)	RAISE Academy Task will be activated only in M24
Thematic Workshops	Community-Building Activities Co-Create Research Challenge Priorities Co-Develop AI Research and Innovation Priorities Foster Cross-Domain Collaboration Establish Cross-Network Synergies Foster Academia-Industry Collaborations	AISWG members	Thematic workshops are being planned M6-M10, in co-location with major community events
AIS Summits participation	Align Outputs with Strategic Initiatives Co-Develop Upgrade Scenarios Support Sustainability Translate AI-Enabled Science into Innovation Ensure SRIA Uptake	Research Communities Research Infrastructures (incl. ESFRI, EOSC, e-Infrastructures, HPC) Policy Makers and Funders Industry and Innovation Actors Civil Society and Societal Stakeholders	AIS26 Dublin: proposal for SCIANCE participation submitted
Participation in External Events	Promote AI in Science Methods Extend Awareness Amplify Outputs Broaden Reach	All	Full list of events available on the Digital Hub, post-even reporting active
Online and offline Consultations	Align Outputs with Strategic Initiatives Co-Develop Upgrade Scenarios Support Sustainability Translate AI-Enabled Science into Innovation Ensure SRIA Uptake	All	
Closing Event	Align Outputs with Strategic Initiatives Co-Develop Upgrade Scenarios Support Sustainability Translate AI-Enabled Science into Innovation Ensure SRIA Uptake	All	

Monitoring & KPIs: All dissemination activities will be subject to rigorous monitoring and evaluation. Web analytics, event participation, stakeholder engagement metrics, and direct feedback will be systematically collected to assess reach, relevance, and impact. This evidence-based approach will allow the strategy to adapt in real-time, optimising visibility, uptake, and stakeholder satisfaction.

6 Work Plan

WP8 (M1-M15) and WP9 (M15-M30) jointly implement SCIANCE's Communication, Engagement, and Sustainability activities across the full project lifecycle. The work is designed to ensure continuous alignment between dissemination, co-creation, and exploitation activities, supporting the progressive development, validation, and uptake of the SRIA and related outputs.

6.1 Key deliverables and milestones

The table below summarises the key deliverables produced under WP8 and WP9:

Key Deliverables						
Deliverable	Title	WP	Lead	Type	Dissemination	Due
D8.1	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy	8	EGI	DEC	PU	M6
D8.2	RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference	8	ESF	R	PU	M3
D9.1	Sustainability and Exploitation Plan	9	ESF	R	PU	M30
D9.2	RAISE Academy Blueprint (including pilot bootcamp evaluation)	9	OpenAIRE	R	PU	M30

The milestones below capture the main implementation and validation points for WP8–WP9 activities:

Key Milestones				
Milestone	Description	WP(s)	Due	Means of Verification
MS1	RAISE Digital Hub and Secretariat operational; AI in Science mapping methodology established	1–8	M7	D8.2, D1.3, Digital Hub live
MS2	AIS Working Groups established; first AIS Summit and CDE framework operational	6–8	M6	D6.4, D8.1, participation lists
MS8	Final SRIA and Roadmap published; AIS Summit #3 and Academy pilot delivered	5–9	M30	D4.2, D5.1, D9.1, D9.2

6.2 Partner responsibilities

WP8–WP9 activities are implemented through a distributed consortium model, ensuring balanced expertise across communication, engagement, technical coordination, policy alignment, and sustainability planning.

Partner	Role in WP8–WP9	Key Responsibilities
EGI	WP8/WP9 Lead	Overall coordination of the WP8/9, communication strategy, Digital Hub development and operation, RAISE forum technical management, AIS Summit and other event organisation, dissemination campaigns
ESF	WP8/9 Contributor, Secretariat Host	RAISE Secretariat setup and operation, sustainability planning (D9.1), governance support, coordination of long-term exploitation, AIS Summit coordination
OpenAIRE	Engagement & Data Lead	Stakeholder mapping and engagement activities (T8.2/9.2), RAISE Forum engagement management, RAISE Academy lead (T9.5), Data integration, consultation tools, Digital Hub contribution
BDVA	Industry & Innovation Interface	Industry engagement, dissemination support, AIS Summit contributions, exploitation pathways
DFKI	Technical & AI Expertise	Support to communication content, stakeholder engagement in AI domains, Digital Hub thematic integration
CU	Research & Engagement Support	Stakeholder engagement, workshop facilitation, content contribution for consultations and SRIA development
EMBL	Scientific Domain Expertise	Scientific community engagement, thematic input to dissemination and events, AIS Summit contributions

SZTAKI	Research & AI Methods Input	Contribution to communication content and dissemination of AI methodologies and outputs
---------------	-----------------------------	---

7 Monitoring, Evaluation, and KPIs

7.1 Key Performance Indicators by Activity

This section consolidates all Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to SCIANCE communication, dissemination, engagement, training, and external participation activities. KPIs are used to monitor reach, effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and uptake of project outputs, ensuring evidence-based management and continuous optimisation of the CDE strategy.

Activity Area	Activity / Measure	Target / KPI	Timing
Early Communication Campaigns	Release campaign (website, newsletter, social media launch)	Channels operational by M1 (ahead of M3 target); 550 newsletter subscribers; 4,225 website visits	M1–M4
	AISWG call campaign	>500 expressions of interest; achieved: 650+ registrations	M1–M4
Communication Channels	Digital Hub usage	>10,000 unique visits by end of project; >500 downloads of resources	M6–M30
	Newsletter	>800 subscribers; open rate >30%	Quarterly
	Social media campaigns	>1,000 followers; average reach ~6,000/month	M4–M30
	Partner amplification	>15 partner channels actively engaged; >50 amplified outputs/year	M4–M30
Events Programme	AIS Summits (3 editions incl. final event)	>250 participants per summit; balanced stakeholder representation; >80 participants final event	M10, M22, M29(TBC)
	Thematic workshops	>10 workshops; >120 total participants	M8–M15
RAISE Academy (Training)	Bootcamps / training sessions	>50 participants per bootcamp; >80% positive feedback	M29
Stakeholder Engagement	Domain scientists engagement	>70 participants in workshops and consultations	M8–M20
	AI experts engagement	>50 experts engaged in co-creation activities	M8–M20
	Infrastructures engagement	>20 infrastructures engaged; alignment with upgrade scenarios	M10–M24
	Policy engagement	>25 policymakers engaged; >250 participants per AIS Summit	M5–M29
	Networks engagement	>10 AI networks engaged; joint activities and outputs	M6–M30
	Civil society engagement	>50 contributors engaged in consultations and outreach	M12–M30
External Participation Strategy	Strategic event participation	>15 external high-level EU/international events	M3–M30
	Policy influence outputs	Contributions to at least 5 policy/strategic discussions	M12–M30

Overall Impact Indicators	SRIA engagement	Iterative consultation cycles with broad stakeholder participation	M10–M26
	Knowledge uptake	Evidence of reuse of outputs (SRIA, roadmap, evidence base) across ecosystems	Post-project
	Ecosystem building	Growth of sustained AI in Science community via RAISE Digital Hub	M6–post-project

7.2 Data Collection and Analytics

SCIANCE implements a structured, evidence-based monitoring and analytics framework to support continuous evaluation and optimisation of CDE activities across WP8 and WP9.

The framework combines digital analytics, stakeholder interaction data, and platform-based behavioural data from the RAISE Digital Hub engagement layer, ensuring robust feedback loops for adaptive management.

The approach is fully aligned with the Data Management Plan (D6.4), which defines data governance, storage, access control, and compliance with EU data protection requirements.

8.2.1 Data Sources and Collection Framework

Data is collected from multiple integrated layers:

7.2.1.1 Digital communication analytics

- Website and Digital Hub usage (traffic, downloads, navigation patterns)
- Social media performance (reach, impressions, engagement rates)
- Newsletter analytics (open rate, click-through rate, subscriptions)

7.2.1.2 Event and engagement data

- AIS Summit participation and registration data
- Workshop and consultation attendance records
- Survey responses and feedback forms

7.2.1.3 RAISE Digital Hub Forum (Discourse)

The RAISE community platform provides a structured environment for co-creation and consultation. Data generated includes:

- Discussion activity (threads, replies, participation rates)
- Working Group engagement metrics (posts, collaborations, contributions)
- Poll and survey responses integrated into consultations
- Tagging and thematic interaction patterns across groups

The platform operates under a three-layer access model (Working Groups, AI & Science Community, Public layer), which directly structures data visibility and collection granularity:

- Working Group layer: high-resolution interaction data (expert discussions, draft co-creation)
- Community layer: aggregated engagement and consultation data
- Public layer: anonymised and curated interaction (forms, surveys, feedback only)

Importantly, raw internal discussions are not publicly accessible, ensuring controlled openness and compliance with governance rules.

7.2.1.4 Stakeholder and partner reporting

- Consortium partner dissemination reports
- External event participation logs
- Communication outputs (presentations, publications, outreach materials)

8.2.2 Governance, Data Protection and Compliance

All data collection and processing activities are governed by the SCIANCE Data Management Plan (D6.5) and the platform-specific governance framework developed for the RAISE Digital Hub.

Key principles include:

- EU data sovereignty: all platform data is stored and processed on EU-based infrastructure
- GDPR compliance: personal data is minimised, controlled, and protected
- Defined user access levels: strict separation between working group, community, and public layers
- Clear data ownership rules: contributors retain intellectual ownership; SCIANCE ensures attribution and controlled reuse
- Code of conduct enforcement: ensures responsible participation and content management
- Where AI-assisted tools are used (e.g. summarisation or moderation support), they must comply with European data and AI governance requirements, and operate under approved infrastructure constraints.

8.2.3 Analytics and Evaluation Framework

Collected data is analysed to assess:

- Reach: visibility across stakeholder groups and channels
- Engagement: depth of interaction across digital and physical spaces
- Participation: stakeholder involvement in co-creation processes
- Contribution quality: relevance and usefulness of inputs to SRIA and roadmap development
- Uptake signals: reuse of outputs across ecosystems, networks, and policy processes

Special attention is given to cross-group interaction patterns within the RAISE forum, as these provide evidence of interdisciplinary collaboration and community formation.

7.3 Adaptive Strategy and Continuous Improvement

The SCIANCE Communication, Dissemination and Engagement strategy is designed as an adaptive framework that evolves continuously based on evidence generated through monitoring, analytics, and stakeholder feedback.

Rather than following a static implementation plan, the strategy integrates structured feedback loops between data collection (Section 8.2), operational delivery (WP8–WP9 activities), and strategic refinement.

8.3.1 Adaptive management cycle

The continuous improvement cycle follows four steps:

- 1 Monitor: collection of quantitative and qualitative data across digital platforms, events, and engagement activities
- 2 Analyse: identification of trends in reach, engagement, participation, and stakeholder interaction patterns
- 3 Interpret: assessment of implications for communication effectiveness, engagement design, and dissemination impact
- 4 Adapt: refinement of tools, campaigns, governance mechanisms, and engagement formats

Areas of adaptation

Insights from analytics and stakeholder feedback are used to iteratively improve:

- Communication campaigns (messaging, targeting, and channel mix)
- Engagement design within the RAISE Digital Hub forum (structure, moderation, access model)
- Consultation and co-creation processes for SRIA and roadmap development
 - Event formats, including AIS Summits, workshops, and training activities
 - Dissemination targeting and stakeholder segmentation strategies

RAISE Digital Hub evolution

A key area of adaptive development is the RAISE Digital Hub engagement layer, which is expected to evolve based on real usage patterns. Adjustments may include:

- refinement of working group structures and tagging systems
- optimisation of consultation workflows (polls, surveys, feedback loops)
- adjustment of moderation models and access levels where needed.

8 Vocabulary

Stakeholder & Engagement Vocabulary	
Term	Guidelines
RAISE	Resource for AI Science in Europe; the longer-term European coordination structure that SCIANCE helps pilot and prepare.
RAISE Digital Hub	The RAISE Digital Hub will act as the central engagement and access layer for SCIANCE/RAISE. It will provide structured, interactive access to SCIANCE outputs, including the evidence base, SRIA, roadmap, good practices, consultation materials and related resources, while also supporting input collection across WP1–WP5 through surveys, feedback tools, thematic forums and Discourse-based consultation spaces. It will enable good-practice submissions, Living SRIA consultation threads, open calls and consultations, and transparent summaries showing how stakeholder input is collected, reviewed and integrated into SRIA and roadmap development. The Hub will not replace WP2/WP3 workshops, AISWG meetings, AIS Summit-linked activities or targeted consultations; instead, it will connect them, preserve their outputs, and provide continuity, visibility and traceability across the engagement process.
RAISE Academy	Capacity-building pilot mainly for ministries, funders, digital officers, and science executives to support informed AI in Science decision-making. The Academy targets decision-makers and is not designed for extensive discipline-specific researcher training.
AIS Summits	Annual AI in Science Summit events are used as high-level consultation, matchmaking, visibility, and validation moments. Stated as SCIANCE activities will be co-located with AIS Summits and use *AIS26–AIS28 as key moments. <i>*Where feasible / according to confirmed AIS Summit schedule</i>
Digital Hub operational model	The separate practical model defines platform access, moderation, permissions, staged rollout, user groups, privacy, and governance arrangements.
AISWG / AI in Science Working Groups	Ten expert working groups supporting SRIA development: five domain-specific groups and five cross-cutting AI-related groups.
Domain AISWGs	AISWGs focused on the five scientific pilot areas: Astronomy & Fundamental Physics, Materials Science, Life Sciences, Earth Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities.
Cross-cutting AISWGs	AISWGs focused on AI-related and transversal topics: AI Research & Experimental Design, Data Science & Advanced Analytics, Open Science & Trustworthy AI, AI & Computing Infrastructures, Industry, Innovation & Frugal AI.
AISWG members	Selected experts participating voluntarily in AISWG activities, including workshops, online meetings, asynchronous feedback, and review of SRIA-related outputs.
AISWG co-chairs	One SCIANCE consortium co-chair and one appointed expert co-chair per AISWG, with possible additional SCIANCE co-chairing for complex groups.
SAB / Strategic Advisory Board	A high-level external advisory body of approximately nine external advisors or representatives able to provide non-binding strategic insight, alignment support and network connections.
RAISE Secretariat	The pilot coordination function hosted by ESF during SCIANCE supports RAISE continuity, AISWG activities, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability.
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for AI in Science: the main strategic output defining priorities and recommendations.

<p>Related RAISE-supporting projects and initiatives</p>	<p>Used when referring to projects, initiatives, and coordination actions connected to the broader RAISE / AI in Science ecosystem. In the current document, they should not be presented as a separate stakeholder category. Instead, they should be treated as cross-cutting ecosystem interfaces that can contribute relevant outputs, networks, expertise, consultation input, and alignment opportunities across several SRIA pillars. Refer to them where their results or communities can support SRIA development, roadmap alignment, stakeholder mobilisation, Digital Hub content, good-practice collection, consultation activities or future RAISE coordination.</p>
<p>ESFRI Research Infrastructures, ERICs and RI clusters</p>	<p>Used when referring to ESFRI-related infrastructure actors that provide scientific data, services, facilities, standards, governance models and user communities. In the current document, these actors are included under the merged stakeholder category Research Infrastructures, E-Infrastructures, & Scientific Facilities. Use ESFRI Research Infrastructures, ESFRI RIs, ERICs, ERIC Forum, RI clusters, or the specific name of the infrastructure where relevant. Avoid the vague phrase “ESFRI organisations”, because it is unclear whether it refers to ESFRI Forum, individual RIs, ERICs, clusters or governance bodies. This term should be used in sections on infrastructure mapping, AI-ready data, infrastructure gap analysis, upgrade scenarios, cooperation mechanisms, roadmap validation and strategic alignment.</p>
<p>EOSC ecosystem</p>	<p>Term to be used when referring to EOSC Association, EOSC nodes, EOSC-related projects, EOSC service providers, EOSC Task Forces, AI4EOSC, OpenAIRE and other Open Science / FAIR data services connected to the EOSC federation. In the current document, EOSC should not be treated as a separate full stakeholder category, but as a key part of the merged category Research Infrastructures, E-Infrastructures & Scientific Facilities and as a strategic alignment interface for the RAISE Digital Hub, infrastructure roadmap, data interoperability, FAIR data, AAI, service integration and Open Science practices.</p>
<p>European AI Research and Innovation Ecosystem Actors</p>	<p>Term to be used for European AI networks, AI centres of excellence, AI research initiatives, AI-on-Demand / AI4EOSC-related initiatives, GenAI / GenAI4EU-related structures, ADRA, ELLIS, CAIRNE and related AI research and innovation communities. In the current document, they should be treated as a cross-cutting interface connected mainly to AI Experts & AI Researchers, Industry & Innovation Actors, and Policy Makers & Funding Organisations, rather than as a separate heavy stakeholder table. Engage them where they support AI for Science priority-setting, technical validation, innovation uptake, standards alignment, Digital Hub content or strategic alignment with European AI initiatives.</p>
<p>Education & Training Stakeholders</p>	<p>Term to be used for universities, doctoral schools, training centres, professional development providers, data stewardship training providers, research support offices and RAISE Academy participants. In the current document, they should be treated as a cross-cutting stakeholder interface connected mainly to Skills & Culture, the RAISE Academy, Digital Hub training resources, and capacity-building activities. They do not need a long standalone table unless the strategy later develops a dedicated Academy or training engagement plan.</p>
<p>Communication Professionals and Multipliers</p>	<p>Term to be used for RI communication officers, science communicators, partner communication teams, institutional press offices, newsletter editors, community managers and dissemination contacts in relevant networks. In the current document, they should be treated as cross-cutting multipliers who support visibility, accessibility and uptake of SCIANCE outputs across all stakeholder groups. They are not a primary SRIA co-creation group, but they are important for targeted campaigns, newsletters, social media, event promotion, Digital Hub visibility and dissemination of SRIA, roadmap and good-practice outputs.</p>
<p>Roadmap / Implementation Roadmap</p>	<p>The AI in Science Roadmap follows a parallel process. WP3 identifies infrastructure gaps, upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms through workshops and targeted consultations with infrastructure actors, AISWG experts and other relevant stakeholders. WP4 assesses the feasibility of these scenarios and develops the roadmap. WP5 then supports validation and strategic alignment of roadmap outputs together with the SRIA. WP1 evidence → WP2 co-creation → Hub/AIS Summit feedback → AISWG review/integration → WP5 strategic alignment</p>

Evidence Base	The WP1 knowledge base includes state-of-the-art reviews, AI in Science landscape mapping, infrastructure directory, and good-practice registry. Used when referring to inputs from WP1 that inform WP2, WP3, WP5, and stakeholder engagement.
Good-practice registry	Public registry of community-validated good practices in AI-enabled science. Used in stakeholder tables where groups can submit, validate, or reuse cases. O#1 specifies a public registry of more than 40 community-validated good practices.
CMO framework	Context–Mechanism–Outcome framework used to analyse good practices and understand under which conditions AI-enabled science practices produce outcomes. Used only in WP1/good-practice context, not as a general engagement method.
Landscape analysis	Structured mapping of AI infrastructure, initiatives, and emerging trends in AI adoption across European scientific domains.
State-of-the-art review	WP1 review of AI-enabled scientific research in the five pilot domains and AI for Science research and innovations. Use the knowledge consolidation phase. The proposal describes T1.1–T1.2 as state-of-the-art analyses informing WP2 priorities
AI in Science	Use of AI to transform scientific research, discovery, methods, and workflows across scientific domains. Use when referring to the overall project theme and domain applications. The proposal frames AI in Science as AI-enabled scientific research across domains.
AI for Science	AI methods, tools and innovations that support scientific processes and workflows across domains. Used when referring to cross-domain AI methods, research lifecycle tools, AI workflows, and technical R&I priorities. The proposal distinguishes AI for Science methods and applications across the scientific lifecycle.
Research communities	Researchers, institutions, scientific networks, and disciplinary communities contribute scientific priorities, use cases, and validation. Used for scientific/domain communities, not as a catch-all for all stakeholders. Scientific communities and domain scientists as primary users and contributors to SRIA priorities.
AI researchers & technology experts	Experts in AI methods, AI systems, AI for Science workflows, trustworthy/frugal AI, data science, foundation models and related technologies. AI researchers and technology experts are a target group shaping AI research priorities.
Research infrastructures, e-infrastructures & scientific facilities	Merged category covering ESFRI/ERICs, EOSC/e-infrastructures, EuroHPC JU/AI compute, scientific facilities and national infrastructures. Use instead of five repetitive infrastructure categories unless a detailed annex is needed. Infrastructures and initiatives are grouped together, including ESFRI RIs, EuroHPC JU, EOSC, AI Factories and e-infrastructures.
Policy makers & funding organisations	EC, Member States, ministries, national research councils, funders, programme committees, policy units and strategic decision-makers. Identified policy makers and funding organisations, as highly influential for adoption, funding and sustainability.
Industry & innovation actors	AI companies, SMEs, tech providers, industry R&D labs, data/cloud/HPC providers, publishers, innovation networks and associations such as BDVA/ADRA. industry and innovation actors relevant for innovation transfer and infrastructure upgrade priorities.
Co-creation	Structured expert and stakeholder contribution to shaping priorities, scenarios and recommendations. Used for feedback and validation processes; specify whether public, targeted or expert consultation. The proposal includes broader iterative consultations through the Digital Hub, AIS Summits, and targeted processes.
Consultation (s)	Structured collection of feedback from selected or wider stakeholder groups through the Hub, workshops, AIS Summits, written input or bilateral discussions. Use feedback and validation processes; specify whether public, targeted, or expert consultation. Included as broader iterative consultations through the Digital Hub, AIS Summits, and targeted processes.

Validation	Review of draft outputs to test relevance, robustness, feasibility, and alignment before finalisation. Used for review moments; avoid implying external bodies formally approve deliverables. SAB provides feedback on relevance, feasibility, and alignment, while recommendations remain in advisory.
Strategic alignment	Mapping and positioning SRIA and roadmap outputs against EU/national strategies, European initiatives, policy frameworks and infrastructure roadmaps. Use especially for WP5, SAB and policy actors.
Targeted consultation	Consultation with a defined group of stakeholders because of their expertise, mandate, or strategic relevance. Used for policy actors, infrastructures, industry networks, SAB input, and WP3/WP5 processes. The proposal refers to targeted consultations for infrastructure scenarios, cooperation mechanisms, and policy alignment.
Public online consultation	Open or broadly accessible consultation through the Digital Hub and partner networks. Use for final SRIA/roadmap feedback and wider ecosystem input. Final SRIA and roadmap validation will use public online consultation through the Digital Hub and partner networks.
Engagement level Co-create	Deep expert contribution to shaping priorities, scenarios or recommendations. Used for AISWGs as co-creation communities supporting SRIA priorities and infrastructure scenarios.
Engagement level Review / Validate	Structured feedback on draft outputs or synthesis documents. Review and feedback roles for SAB and AISWG, respectively.
Engagement level Advise	High-level, non-binding strategic input. SAB acts solely in an advisory, non-binding role.
Engagement level Consult	Stakeholders provide input, feedback, or views on specific questions, drafts or scenarios. Used for civil society, policy, industry, infrastructure and extended community.
Confidentiality	Protection of non-public drafts, discussions and materials shared with AISWG/SAB members.
Traceability of input	Ability to show how stakeholder feedback was collected, summarised and considered in outputs. Used as a principle for the Hub, consultation summaries, and engagement reporting.